

eDNAAqua-Plan

NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Standards for eDNA repositories

Deliverable 3.2

Work Package 3

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Executive summary

Environmental DNA (eDNA) is reshaping aquatic biodiversity monitoring by enabling scalable, cross-ecosystem species detection. Its broader societal and scientific value, however, is constrained by fragmented data governance, inconsistent metadata practices, and limited interoperability between standards. eDNA data is produced by a wide range of actors using partially overlapping, but misaligned metadata standards, which hinders data discoverability, integration, reuse, and interpretation across systems and jurisdictions.

This deliverable addresses these barriers through Task 3.2 of eDNAqua-Plan, which focuses on improving interoperability by aligning community (meta)data standards across the full aquatic eDNA biomonitoring workflow, from field sampling and laboratory processing to sequencing and bioinformatic analysis. Where relevant, it also accounts for the diversity of eDNA data types, including metabarcoding datasets, mitogenomes, and metagenomes.

Stakeholder-driven use-case evaluations were used to assess the perceived importance and feasibility of metadata terms in real-world submission contexts. These evaluations provide evidence-based insight into current practices and inform recommendations on which metadata elements are primed for standardisation to balance (meta)data quality and reporting burden.

The main technical outcome is two alignment models using the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM). One aligns the GBIF/OBIS DNA-derived extension with Genome Standards Consortium (GSC) MlxS Core; the other formalises and updates the alignment between the Barcode Core Data Model (used by Barcode of Life Data Systems, BOLD) and MlxS Core. Together, these models enable practical interoperability while revealing structural misalignments, unclear term provenance, and coordination gaps between standards bodies and biodiversity infrastructures.

The report also highlights the critical role of metadata in ensuring traceability, provenance, and adequate reuse of eDNA data. Persistent links between sequence data, source material, and spatiotemporal context are essential for data quality, reproducibility, and compliance with Access and Benefit Sharing frameworks, including the Nagoya Protocol and the Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction agreement.

Finally, the deliverable identifies governance challenges that must be addressed to ensure long-term impact, including sustained ownership and maintenance of alignment models beyond project lifetimes, stronger coordination between standards organisations, and mechanisms to manage misalignment as standards evolve.

Overall, this deliverable provides immediate, actionable outputs through alignment models and practical recommendations towards a sustainable, interoperable European eDNA digital ecosystem. Improving metadata interoperability is a necessary prerequisite for the reliable, large-scale use of eDNA data in monitoring biodiversity and informing evidence-based policy.

Table of contents

Document information	1
Executive summary	2
Table of contents	3
1. Introduction	6
2. eDNA initiatives and repositories: (Meta)data Overview	11
2.1. The current eDNA data landscape	11
2.2. eDNA Biomonitoring: General and Workflow-Specific (Meta)Data	13
3. (Meta)Data Standards in eDNA Platforms	15
3.1. WP2 D2.2 findings: major metadata gaps in eDNA repositories	16
3.2. (Meta)Data Terms and Requirements Across eDNA Platforms	16
3.3. WP4 Use Cases: Community Practices for Reporting eDNA Metadata	18
3.3.1 International Sequence Database Consortium (INSDC) repository	19
3.3.2 Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) repository	20
3.3.3 Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) repository	21
3.3.4 FAIR eDNA (FAIRe) Metadata checklist	22
4. Data Mapping	23
4.1. Introduction to Metadata Alignment Models	23
4.2. Mapping Approach	25
4.3. Alignment Models	28
4.3.1. GBIF/OBIS's DNA-Derived extension and the MixS Alignment Model	28
4.3.2. Barcode Core Data Model and MixS Core Alignment Model	31
4.4. Identified Misalignments	34
4.5. Critical Requirements for Future Mappings	36
4.6. Key Outcomes and Next Steps	36
5. Recommendations	41
5.1 General Guidance	41
5.2 Prepare and regularly update a Data Management Plan	41
5.3 Prepare and Submit Raw eDNA Sequences to a Public Repository	41
5.4 Prepare and Submit Processed eDNA Sequences and Taxonomic Assignments to a Public Repository	42
5.5 Missing Tools	43
5.6 Sustainable Metadata Alignment	44
6. Discussion	45
7. Acknowledgements	48
8. Bibliography	48
9. Annexes	51

Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
ABS	Access and Benefit Sharing
ASV	Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs) are a high-resolution method in molecular biodiversity studies that identify sequence variations at a single-nucleotide level
BBNJ	Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction
BCDM	Barcode Core Data Model
BGE	Biodiversity Genomics Europe
BiCIKL	Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library
BIOPOLIS	Associação BIOPOLIS
BOLD	Barcode of Life Data Systems
D[0-9.]	Project deliverable number
DDBJ	DNA Database of Japan
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DwC	Darwin Core, the data standard from TDWG and used by GBIF and OBIS
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
ENA	European Nucleotide Database at the EMBL-EBI
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FAIRe	FAIR eDNA (FAIRe) Metadata Checklist
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GGBN	Global Genome Biodiversity Network
GSC	Genome Standards Consortium, the standards body behind MIxS
INSDC	International Sequence Database Consortium: NCBI(GenBank), ENA and DDBJ
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management Systems
M[0-9]	Project milestone
MIQE	Minimum Information for Publication of Quantitative Real-Time PCR Experiments
MIxS	Genome Standards Consortium (GSC) Minimal Information about (X) a Sequence, the main sample metadata used by the INSDC
NCBI	The US National Centre for Biotechnology Information. Includes GenBank and SRA
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System, part of UNESCO
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs)
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
SRA	Sequence Read Archive (available at the NCBI, ENA, and DDBJ)
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings
SYKE	Finnish Environmental Institute
T[0-9.]	Task number

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
TDWG	The taxonomic database working group, the body behind the DwC standard
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee
WP	Work Package(s)

1. Introduction

Barriers to eDNA Data Sharing and Interoperability

Environmental DNA (eDNA) methods are revolutionising the collection of biodiversity data across all ecosystems worldwide (Laamanen et al., 2025; Blackman et al., 2024). While the new techniques are generating an unforeseen wealth of information on organisms in the environment, the use of this information for research, environmental administration and policy is severely limited by the fragmentation and heterogeneity of data governance (Oliver et al., 2021).

eDNA data is produced by a wide range of actors operating within partially overlapping communities. In the European aquatic eDNA community alone, national or regional government agencies typically conduct routine biomonitoring. At the same time, method development, validation, and ecological interpretation are largely driven by researchers working in universities, national research institutes or short-term funded projects. eDNA data is consequently stored and shared across a multitude of repositories, using disparate data standards and requiring considerable expertise in the data-sharing landscape. Currently employed incentive structures further exacerbate fragmentation of eDNA data storage and sharing: scientific researchers are primarily rewarded for research output in papers rather than for the long-term curation and sharing of interoperable datasets to advance open science (Fecher et al., 2017; Devriendt et al., 2021). On the other hand, data from governmental monitoring programs may be archived in specific agencies or government repositories with limited public access.

The scattered nature of repositories, monitoring efforts, and research groups, coupled with current resource limitations, is not conducive to efficient data integration and interoperability. This fragmentation was demonstrated in eDNAqua-plan D2.2 (Woollard et al., 2025), where we reported poor coverage and heterogeneous metadata practices in eDNA repositories. The challenges related to eDNA metadata publishing are further elaborated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Mind map illustrating key challenges in eDNA metadata publishing, derived from a manual review of selected literature. A higher-resolution version of the figure and complete bibliographic references are available on Page 26 of eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 5 (Babo et al., 2024; <https://zenodo.org/records/14967949>).

Standardised (Meta)data in the eDNA Biomonitoring Workflow

To understand the metadata and data standards needed for eDNA repositories, it is essential to consider the complete biomonitoring workflow. A typical eDNA study involves several consecutive steps: field sample collection, laboratory processing including DNA extraction and library preparation, sequencing, and bioinformatic analysis culminating in taxonomic assignment. Each step generates specific data and metadata types that must be documented to ensure the research is reproducible and the data are reusable. From this point onwards, eDNA sequences, whether raw or processed, are considered primary data, and all pertaining information is considered metadata.

A critical factor for eDNA data interoperability and reuse is the availability of comprehensive, well-structured metadata, i.e. information that describes a resource's provenance, experimental context, processing steps, and analytical assumptions (Table 1). To ensure metadata is readily accessible, reusable, and comprehensible, standardised characteristics that define data interoperability are essential (Gürdür & Asplund, 2018). This formalisation requires field experts to reach consensus on the information needed to describe resources for uniform access and data reuse accurately. Assessing and improving current international efforts to implement standards for eDNA data repositories is therefore crucial for developing a sustainable digital ecosystem that enhances data interoperability within aquatic biomonitoring and enables more effective environmental management and conservation strategies.

Table 1. Definition of some core terms as used here in the eDNA data ecosystem.

Term	Definition
Bioinformatics Metadata	Describes the computational-based aspects of the processing and analysis. Includes the software parameters, filtering, etc.
Data	Scientific data created during research and/or monitoring.
Dataset	Digital object(s) that include the results of the experiment/activity.
Laboratory Metadata	Describes how samples were treated after collection and storage. E.g. DNA extraction, amplification, sequencing.
Interoperable ¹	Data can be readily integrated with other data(sets). In addition, the data needs to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.
Machine readable ¹	The capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with minimal human intervention
Metadata	Metadata contained in or attached to datasets that provide relevant context, e.g. about the provenance, about the experimental setup, about bioinformatics, to provide discovery and description, etc.
Mapping	Aligning terms from different vocabularies together.
Occurrence	The existence of an organism at a place and time.
Reference library	The reference (data) used to derive a result (e.g., eDNA, taxonomic classifications) via a (programmatic) comparison.
Sample	Material samples collected in the field.
Sample Metadata	Describes where and how samples were collected, processed and stored.

Table 1. Definition of some core terms as used here in the eDNA data ecosystem.

Term	Definition
Broker	A broker is an intermediary organisation or service that aids data providers/generators, facilitating the logistics of data generation and management at several points of the aquatic eDNA monitoring workflow. These services span data management and formatting through submission, including support for sequencing and taxonomy.
Standard ⁸	A (meta)data “standard” means any type of agreed-upon set of formats, schemas, vocabularies and methods for sharing/exposing data to ensure findability and accessibility. Ideally, these are defined by an international standards body.
Project/Study Metadata	Describes the overall project, e.g. investigators, dates, places, and related publications.

The practice of annotating datasets is fundamental to data reusability and long-term value. As noted by Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), “the metadata and data should tell a complete story in such a way that new, uninformed users can use this evidence without any additional consultations or correspondence” (Kessy et al., 2023). Achieving this ideal requires that both data and metadata be structured according to recognised standards, enabling computational systems to effectively discover, access, and reuse eDNA data with minimal human intervention.

The scientific and societal value of eDNA extends beyond data generation and depends heavily on the quality, completeness, and accessibility of associated metadata that describe sampling, laboratory, and bioinformatic procedures. Implementing robust data standards delivers multiple benefits for the eDNA research domain. Comprehensive metadata enables tracking of data provenance, ensuring that records are integrated only once and that properties such as geographic location or biome are correctly attributed. This traceability is essential for data quality assurance and reproducibility. Beyond ensuring the integrity of individual studies, standardised metadata allows eDNA data to be integrated with other environmental datasets. Conforming to global eDNA standards enables interoperability and seamless integration with diverse complementary information sources. For example, the European Digital Twin of the Ocean⁹ ambition requires physicochemical measurements such as salinity, satellite observations, and eDNA observational data to build a robust model. Mapping fields such as latitude, longitude, depth, and collection date enables data to be integrated in powerful, unambiguous ways.

The provenance of data records is fundamental to biodiversity research infrastructures for many reasons, most notably to ensure traceability and prevent the redundant integration of the same record across systems. Accurate provenance allows users to verify that associated properties, such as geographic location, biome, or collection context, are correctly mapped and interpreted. Beyond technical integrity, complete and persistent provenance information is essential for meeting multilateral agreements on the use of biological data and digital sequence information, including the Nagoya protocol and the recently ratified Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) agreement.

⁸ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁹

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters/european-digital-twin-ocean-european-dto_en

Continuous linkage back to the original data sources, encompassing both spatial origins and the individuals or institutions responsible for collecting and curating the material, encourages transparent Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) and supports FAIR and lawful reuse of data. In this context, initiatives such as the Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library (BiCIKL) play a critical role by promoting best practices and technical solutions to strengthen traceability across heterogeneous data domains. By encouraging explicit links between sequence data, source material, and their spatiotemporal origins, BiCIKL has demonstrated how improved provenance workflows can enhance interoperability while simultaneously supporting ABS compliance and responsible data use.

Currently, while some basic building blocks have established data packaging standards, such as GA4GH's BAM and CRAM formats, or *de facto* standards like FASTQ, many components of the eDNA workflow, such as ASV/OTU tables, lack standardisation, limiting automated processing and integration. Ultimately, consistent data structuring ensures that information can move seamlessly across systems using defined exchange protocols, enabling researchers to leverage diverse analytical tools and platforms without the burden of manual data reformatting (Kessy et al., 2023).

Alignment Models as a Path Forward

To address the fragmentation of metadata standards and practices, alignment models offer a systematic solution. These models identify common elements and differences across standards and develop mappings or translation rules that allow data formatted in one standard to be understood and used by other systems. In the remainder of this report, the terms 'mapping' and 'alignment' are used interchangeably.

The Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM) provides a community-driven framework for facilitating the exchange and integration of semantic entity mappings (Matentzoglou et al., 2022). This deceptively simple yet powerful tool enables users to align metadata from different sources systematically. Notably, in combination with vocabularies such as the Simple Knowledge Organization System Primer (SKOS) vocabulary (<https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-primer/>), it allows differentiation between narrow, broad, and exact matches of metadata fields, thus accommodating different granularities of terms to be mapped with flexibility and precision.

A decade ago, a semantic and syntactic mapping of core terms was created between the Darwin Core (DwC) and the Minimal Information about any Sequence (MIxS) metadata reporting checklist, enabling the integration of data from these sources (Meyer et al., 2023). However, interoperability remains incomplete. With the increasing use of eDNA, many additional DwC and MIxS field names have been introduced or modified, requiring updated mappings to maintain interoperability.

The eDNAqua-Plan Contribution

The eDNAqua-Plan project (<https://ednaquaplan.com/>) addresses these challenges by developing recommendations to support a more harmonised and interoperable European digital landscape for eDNA data, with a focus on data from aquatic environments. This is achieved by analysing the current landscape and existing practices to identify the most critical interoperability gaps, and by proposing targeted solutions to address them. Building on previous project outputs assessing the coverage of eDNA repositories (eDNAqua-plan D2.2, Woollard et al., 2025, Kavakiotis et al., in press) and mapping the whole digital eDNA landscape (eDNAqua-Plan M7, Boulanger et al., 2025), this deliverable report contributes to the overall project objectives through three complementary outcomes.

Firstly, Chapter 2 gives an overview of the current eDNA (meta)data landscape and compiles the main metadata standards and checklists currently used for eDNA data reporting, facilitating comparison of (meta)data terms across eDNA platforms, including their requirements, descriptions, and other relevant information where available.

Secondly, Chapter 3 highlights the current metadata gaps in eDNA repositories and evaluates stakeholder agreement on the required status of metadata terms, whether they should be mandatory, recommended, or optional, when submitting eDNA data, based on use-case responses collected from representatives involved in the submission of eDNA data.

Thirdly, and as the primary outcome of this work, Chapter 4 delivers two alignment models for key eDNA-relevant metadata checklists. These alignment models are intended to support interoperability by clarifying semantic and syntactic correspondences between standards, thereby facilitating future cross-system data exchange.

Finally, Chapter 5 provides concrete recommendations for data producers to improve their data management practices and highlights bottlenecks and gaps that repositories and standardisation communities should strive to address in continuous exchange with the user and expert community.

2. eDNA initiatives and repositories: (Meta)data Overview

Where repositories implement standards for metadata and data, interoperability improves significantly. In the biodiversity research and monitoring communities, two major metadata standards are in place. DwC, used by the GBIF and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS), provides a comprehensive vocabulary for biodiversity occurrence data, emphasising spatial distribution, ecological diversity, ecosystem types, and taxonomic information. And, the MlxS checklists, maintained by the Genome Standards Consortium (GSC) and used by the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) databases (NCBI, ENA, DDBJ), define minimum metadata requirements for sequence data, with specific extensions for environmental samples such as Minimal Information about a Marker Sequence (MIMARKS), MIMS (Metagenome or Environmental), and Minimum Information About a Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MIMAG). Typically, INSDC databases are used for “raw” sequence data, which can include removal of technical sequences (e.g. primers). Processed sequence data that have undergone filtering, quality control and taxonomic annotation may also be deposited at INSDC, though with some limitations for metabarcoding-derived data. ENA is currently developing a dedicated submission pathway for such metabarcoding processed data in an interoperable format. Alternatively, these processed and taxonomically annotated data, excluding technical samples (e.g., blanks, positive and negative controls), may be deposited in biodiversity repositories such as GBIF or OBIS.

As eDNA data is becoming increasingly important for biodiversity research due to its large volume and efficient collection methods, there is also an increasing need to share the biodiversity insights resulting from this data. To address this need, over the last 5 years, the biodiversity databases OBIS and GBIF have begun integrating eDNA (metabarcoding) data. In this case, most eDNA terms are directly taken from the MlxS checklists, anticipating interoperability across these large databases. The biodiversity databases provide comprehensive data access based on location, time, and taxonomic classification metadata, thereby offering a complementary service to the INSDC databases.

Marker gene and metabarcoding data are therefore shared using both MlxS extensions for raw sequence data deposited in INSDC, and DwC occurrence terms for the resulting taxonomic occurrences deposited in GBIF or OBIS (depending on the different requirements of the relevant databases). Metagenomes can be shared in INSDC databases following the MlxS, MIMS or MIMAG checklists. There is currently no agreed-upon standard for sharing metagenomic data in biodiversity databases; however, this is under active discussion. Throughout this deliverable, we consider metagenomic data to be data obtained from the sequencing of all genetic material in an environmental sample, without PCR amplification of a target.

Depositing eDNA-derived datasets in accessible repositories, along with standardised metadata and adopted reporting formats, such as the Minimum Information about any Sequence (MlxS) and the Darwin Core Archive (DWC-A) standard, ensures that the data is findable, interoperable, and reusable. Overall, the adoption of such standards allows the integration with global biodiversity databases, supports reproducibility, enables comparisons across studies, and maximises the long-term value of eDNA data for research, conservation, and policy-making.

2.1. The current eDNA data landscape

The current aquatic eDNA landscape comprises several fragmented and poorly connected resources, leading to an overall lack of FAIRness in eDNA data and preventing it from being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (Figure 2; see eDNAqua-plan M7 for further details; Boulanger et al., 2025). Comprehensive sampling metadata are essential for describing how, where, when, and by whom the samples were collected, thereby providing key provenance information and context for interpretation and reuse by potential future users. When downstream molecular data are deposited in specific repositories such as the INSDC, associated sample metadata is typically made

available through BioSamples. Also, during the submission process, data providers are requested to share project-level information in BioProject, which captures the broader experimental context. However, some data providers instead deposit their data in generalist repositories, where links between molecular data, sample metadata, and project-level context are often incomplete, further exacerbating this fragmentation and limiting data reuse. Specific repositories are not without issues: the quantity and quality of metadata fields are usually suboptimal, which also limits reuse and interoperability.

Metadata describing laboratory procedures, encompassing all methods from DNA extraction to the generation of raw sequences, can be captured within repositories, such as INSDC, with BioSamples and experiment objects allowing the inclusion of SOPs via DOIs or URLs. For laboratories that use Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS), metadata capture can be automated, although this is more frequent in larger facilities. Structured protocol repositories, such as protocols.io, also exist for sharing methods. However, many laboratories do not consistently publish or link their protocols, with methods often described only in scientific manuscripts. As a result, metadata fields in repositories are frequently underused or incomplete.

Furthermore, no universal standards currently exist for laboratory procedures or their metadata, and machine-readable protocols remain rare, limiting reproducibility, interoperability, and the effective reuse of eDNA data. The raw sequences, usually provided as standardised FASTQ files with minimal processing, can be deposited in FAIR repositories, such as INSDC, which require minimal compulsory metadata (also resulting in incomplete interoperability). However, it is estimated that around 75% of eDNA-generated data is deposited outside the INSDC (see the eDNAqua-Plan D2.2 deliverable for more details; Woollard et al., 2025). In addition, data generated by monitoring programs is often deposited in agency or government repositories that are not publicly available.

From raw sequences to meaningful biological data, bioinformatics analysis of eDNA data involves multiple steps, including quality filtering, read merging, denoising and/or clustering, taxonomic assignment and the production of ASV or OTU tables. These workflows may vary depending on experimental design, sequencing technology, and software choices, thereby influencing biodiversity assessment results. While workflow management systems, such as Snakemake or Nextflow, and code repositories, such as GitHub or ELIXIR WorkflowHubs, exist to document pipelines, metadata describing parameters, computational environments, and output details are often incomplete, limiting reproducibility and reuse. Although Woollard et al. (2025) showed that LLMs could infer bioinformatic workflows from scientific papers, it would be preferable if these metadata were systematically captured and deposited alongside the data.

For taxonomic assignment, reference libraries range from broad nucleotide databases, such as ENA or GenBank, to taxonomically curated databases. Workflows now exist for depositing processed, taxonomically annotated eDNA data to OBIS and GBIF using the DwC-A format, thereby gaining many benefits from FAIR data sharing. Processed eDNA data is rarely deposited in standardised repositories. When the assigned sequences are deposited, metadata is often incomplete. The majority of biodiversity data derived from eDNA are still shared only in supplementary materials or generalist platforms (Dryad, Zenodo, Figshare), which do not enforce metadata standards or formats, thus hampering further reuse and interoperability. Biodiversity monitoring datasets are often stored in non-public agency repositories, further restricting access. Overall, inconsistent metadata, fragmented deposition practices, and limited standardisation hinder the findability, interoperability, reproducibility, and reuse of eDNA data.

Figure 2. The current digital landscape for eDNA from marine, freshwater or transitional waters. A high-resolution version of the image is available in eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 7 (Boulanger et al., 2025; https://zenodo.org/records/16367374/preview/eDNAqua-PlanWP3_landscapeProposal_v1_current.pdf?include_deleted=0).

2.2. eDNA Biomonitoring: General and Workflow-Specific (Meta)Data

The sequences generated through eDNA-based monitoring provide valuable biodiversity observations, rather than solely molecular sequence data. To ensure their use in scientific and regulatory contexts beyond the scope of their original studies, they need to be publicly archived and accompanied by a minimum set of structured metadata. Such metadata provides the context necessary for interpretation, discovery, and reuse. Ideally, metadata and data should enable any user, including those unfamiliar with the original study or monitoring program, to understand the dataset without the need for external consultation (Aberenkov et al., 2023). As previously mentioned, when these observations are associated with geographic coordinates and temporal information, they become even more informative. They can be easily discovered through biodiversity platforms, such as GBIF or OBIS, provided they are properly archived.

To make eDNA datasets truly useful beyond their original contexts, metadata should follow a few key principles. Central among these is compliance with the FAIR framework. Importantly, not all repositories fully support all aspects of this framework. For instance, general-purpose repositories such as Dryad prioritise accessibility and findability, but offer limited support for community-specific metadata standards, which can reduce interoperability and constrain reuses in specific contexts. Nonetheless, for the repositories that do adhere to biodiversity-specific metadata standards, providing information beyond the mandatory terms greatly improves the long-term utility of the datasets. This thorough metadata reporting, in turn, also enhances discoverability while facilitating reuse and integration with other biodiversity datasets.

As previously mentioned, metadata associated with eDNA-derived datasets span the entire workflow, from project design and sampling to laboratory processing, sequencing, and data analyses.

Across this workflow, the different types of data and metadata generated at specific stages can be deposited in a combination of specialised and general-purpose repositories, depending on their content, level of processing, and intended reuse (Figure 3). Metadata can therefore be organised into clear categories, which can help ensure that datasets are interpretable, reusable and traceable:

- A) Project-level metadata** provides context on why and by whom a study was conducted. Under this section, one may include the project title, a brief description and its main objectives, along with authors and their affiliations, funding sources, and persistent identifiers such as DOIs. Project-level metadata will support traceability, enabling proper citation, and allow users to link multiple datasets or different versions of the same dataset within a single project. Typically, this information can be submitted to INSDC.
- B) Sample-level Metadata** captures where, when, and how samples were collected. It typically includes geographical coordinates, environmental context, collection date and time, and collection procedures. Such information is essential for interpreting eDNA-derived data as biodiversity observation and for enabling discoverability through occurrence-based platforms such as GBIF and OBIS. Registering samples in repositories such as Biosample further supports this process by assigning unique identifiers that link physical samples to derived sequence data. Sample-level metadata should comply with a suitable checklist to capture essential information.
- C) Experiment-level metadata** describes how samples were processed and how DNA was captured and recorded, supporting reproducibility. Essential elements include DNA extraction, laboratory workflows, target markers, and PCR primers and conditions. While metadata requirements at this level are often limited or inconsistently enforced across repositories, laboratory protocols and workflows can be documented in complementary resources such as protocols.io or through community-driven templates, including those developed and available under the Better Biomolecular Ocean Practices ([BeBOP](https://github.com/BeBOP)) Github. The latter hosts a variety of method templates, including MIOP (Minimum Information about an Omics Protocol, https://github.com/BeBOP-OBON/0_protocol_collection_template/blob/main/MIOP_definition.md) and FAIR metadata fields to enhance interoperability. The FAIR metadata checklist is a global, community-led initiative convened by Miwa Takahashi at CSIRO (the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation). It was developed to extend and improve existing (meta)data standards for eDNA-based studies, thereby enhancing FAIR compliance across the field. The checklist integrates widely adopted terms from established genomic and biodiversity standards, while also introducing novel terms specifically designed for eDNA applications. Alongside raw sequence data, metadata describing sequencing strategies, file formats, and data integrity checks (e.g. checksums) should be provided. Maintaining persistent links between these raw sequences, original samples, and derived biodiversity observations ensures not only transparency but also enables re-analysis and/or reuse.
- D) Bioinformatics and taxonomic metadata** document how the raw sequences were analysed. These include information on bioinformatic workflows, software versions, taxonomic assignment methods, reference databases, and parameter settings. Such metadata provides essential context for the eDNA-based occurrences obtained, while also enabling other users to evaluate the reliability of the results, reproduce analyses, and even integrate datasets across studies. Updated analysis or new versions of the same dataset can be linked under the same DOI, improving traceability. Despite their importance, bioinformatics methods have historically been underrepresented in metadata standards. However, the recent extensions of DNA-related terms in Darwin Core and the FAIR framework are beginning to address this gap. For sequences without taxonomic assignment, they should be deposited in OBIS, GBIF, or INSDC, as it is expected that increased efforts to populate reference databases will, in the future, allow their identification. Additionally, in cases where the sequence itself cannot be deposited, it is suggested to archive them using an MD5 checksum instead, along with their expected

scientific name, as this method would still allow for data integration and comparison with other datasets (Abarenkov et al., 2025).

Figure 3. Simplified version of the proposed future digital landscape of eDNA data, highlighting which types of data and metadata are produced at different key steps of an eDNA metabarcoding workflow. The databases and metadata standards given here are merely a subset of the many possibilities in the current landscape, but show the main ones considered in this deliverable. For the complete, high-quality future landscape, please refer to eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 7 (Boulanger et al., 2025).

Overall, whenever possible, metadata should adhere to recognised schemas, include persistent identifiers such as DOIs and BioSample IDs, and comply with FAIR principles. Using comprehensive, well-structured metadata is fundamental for maximising the long-term value, interoperability, and impact of eDNA-derived biodiversity data. This includes not only linking datasets, protocols, or reference databases stored in other repositories, but also using standardised terms and controlled vocabularies, such as NCBI Taxonomy for species or ENVO for environmental descriptors, so that the data can be understood, compared, and reused easily across studies and platforms.

3. (Meta)Data Standards in eDNA Platforms

To propose an effective model of required alignments for eDNA metadata, it is necessary to evaluate ongoing standardisation efforts. This step will build on the output of T2.2, which aimed to identify and review gaps in existing metadata standards.

3.1. WP2 D2.2 findings: major metadata gaps in eDNA repositories

The major gaps identified during the inventory and investigation of eDNA databases are detailed in the WP2 D2.2 Report of eDNA Data Repositories (Woollard et al., 2025). The results are summarised below.

The investigation of existing eDNA databases revealed a series of substantial gaps that affect data discoverability, interoperability, and long-term usability. A significant issue is that raw eDNA sequence data is heavily scattered across many repositories, with as much as half residing outside the central INSDC archives. This fragmentation makes data difficult to locate, query, and reuse, and smaller archives may be at greater risk of data loss over time. Even in the scientific literature, information on where eDNA sequences are stored is inconsistently reported: depending on the method, only about 50-77% of papers clearly reference the storage location.

Technical inconsistency across repositories also poses a barrier. Each archive typically exposes its own API with little standardisation, and identifiers for eDNA data are often difficult to retrieve programmatically, complicating federated search efforts. Many repositories lack essential sample or sequence metadata, such as GPS coordinates or library strategy, and a large majority (41 of 61 surveyed) have no stated processed-metadata standards. Although some repositories employ global metadata standards such as DwC or MixS, many others do not, especially when data is stored informally (e.g., in supplementary files or in general-purpose repositories such as Dryad). Even where standards exist, users sometimes opt for more generic INSDC checklists with fewer mandatory fields, reducing downstream searchability.

Several issues specific to aquatic eDNA are present in the INSDC archives. It is difficult to reliably query for aquatic environmental samples because the necessary metadata fields are often missing or inconsistently applied. Data formats beyond FASTA and FASTQ vary widely, further reducing interoperability. Barcode gene information, critical for interpreting eDNA obtained from metabarcoding or targeted assays, rarely appears in the “target_gene” field, and only about 20% of studies record it in titles or descriptions, as INSDC does not mandate barcode marker identifiers (Woollard et al., 2025). In addition, the taxonomy associated with submitted sequences is static at the time of upload and does not automatically update as reference libraries evolve. When the taxonomic backbone, such as the NCBI taxonomy database, is updated, the corresponding taxonomic names in sequence records are automatically updated. However, updates that require reinterpretation or reidentification of a sequence based on new information are not applied automatically and can currently be made only by the original submitter or through third-party curation added to the record.

Geographical representation is also uneven. Sampling and archival activity appear disproportionately low in Eastern Europe, despite the region’s diverse aquatic environments. Finally, across most repositories, it is difficult to explicitly identify or count eDNA records, whether raw or processed, underscoring the challenges of inventorying global eDNA resources.

3.2. (Meta)Data Terms and Requirements Across eDNA Platforms

Each of the major eDNA repositories (INSDS, OBIS, GBIF, and BOLD) provides checklists, some of which are tailored to specific environments. INSDC members (NCBI, ENA, DDBJ) increasingly base their sample-level packages/checklists on MixS standards (<https://genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io/mixs/>); for example, ENA’s (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>) implementation includes the “GSC MixS water” checklist, which is particularly relevant for aquatic eDNA. INSDC’s approach focuses on sample description and sequence-centric metadata, whereas GBIF (<https://www.gbif.org/standards>) follows a

more observation-oriented approach. OBIS (<https://manual.obis.org/>) adopts a similar biodiversity-occurrence framework, with a stronger focus on marine contexts.

In addition to repository-level checklists, project-level frameworks also influence eDNA metadata reporting practices. BioProjects (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/>) provides a mechanism within INSDC for grouping related samples and sequencing outputs under a shared scientific context, supporting consistent project-level description across studies. The Tree of Life (ToL, <https://www.darwintreeoflife.org/>) project, while primarily focused on terrestrial and freshwater taxa around Britain and Ireland, forms part of the broader European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA, <https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>) initiative and applies a defined set of metadata requirements enforced through ENA. Within this framework, sequencing is typically carried out by participating institutes, with metadata submission and standards compliance supported by established brokers and infrastructures such as the Wellcome Sanger Institute (<https://www.sanger.ac.uk/>) and COPO (Collaborative OPen Omics, <https://copo-project.org/>).

Despite these differing emphases, a core set of metadata can be expected to be consistently available across repositories. At a minimum, all require or strongly recommend taxonomic assignment, collection date, and geographic information, including coordinates and country or sea. BOLD serves a complementary function in this ecosystem, primarily as a repository for reference barcode sequences, with typically fewer associated metadata requirements.

Before initiating the mapping effort, the team compiled the main metadata checklists currently used for eDNA data reporting in Europe to facilitate comparison of (meta)data terms across eDNA platforms and to support newcomers to metadata reporting practices in the eDNA field. The collected checklists included the “Tree of Life Checklist” (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERC000053>), the “ENA default” sample checklist and ENA’s adopted GSC’s MlxS environmental packages, the FAIRe checklist (<https://fair-edna.github.io/download.html#faire-metadata-checklist>), the GBIF’s and OBIS’s DNA-derived data extension, in addition to OBIS-recommended fields and GBIF-recommended fields. For each entry, we recorded the originating repository, checklist name, field name, identifier and URI (where available), the term description as defined by the source standard, requirement status, and additional comments where necessary.

The ENA checklists, including their field names, required status, and definitions, were originally collated using SQL queries that joined multiple tables within the ENA Oracle instance maintained by EMBL-EBI. Following the migration of sample data from ENA to BioSample, in summer 2025, equivalent information can now be retrieved programmatically via the BioSample schema-store API endpoints (e.g. curl -s '<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/schema-store/api/v2/schemas/list>'). The FAIRe checklist (version 1.0.0) was downloaded in Excel format from the initiative’s official website (<https://fair-edna.github.io/download.html#faire-metadata-checklist>). Recommended field checklists from OBIS (<https://manual.obis.org/checklist.html#darwin-core-term-checklist-for-obis>) and GBIF (<https://docs.gbif.org/publishing-dna-derived-data/en/#data-mapping>) were sourced from their respective online manuals, which describe best practices for data contribution and access and explicitly enumerate relevant Darwin Core terms.

The compilation process resulted in an aggregated reference table of eDNA metadata reporting checklists, providing a consolidated overview of commonly used terms across major standards and initiatives. This compiled reference supports cross-standard comparison, facilitates metadata reporting for new data providers, and serves as the basis for the subsequent semantic and syntactic mapping activities. The resulting resource is publicly accessible at <https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/D3.2-Standards-for-eDNA-repositories/tree/main/edna-metadata-indices>.

As for follow-up efforts, a more detailed comparison of the required status and workflow-step coverage across the main eDNA checklists could be built on this reference resource to identify areas of overlap, duplication of effort, and gaps in coverage. Such analysis would also enable comparison of how well individual checklists support specific workflow stages and whether certain checklists provide more complete or appropriate coverage for particular eDNA use cases.

As a more ambitious extension, metadata terms could be annotated to indicate the levels at which they are applicable or reusable (e.g. project, sampling event, sample or sequence level), thereby reducing redundancy and effort during data submission. For example, specific terms defined at the sample level may also be valid and reusable at the project level without modification.

3.3. WP4 Use Cases: Community Practices for Reporting eDNA Metadata

Building on the metadata checklist compilation described in Section 3.2, a subset of platforms and checklists was selected to further evaluate metadata submission practices through WP4 use cases. The checklists adopted by the INSDC, OBIS, and GBIF platforms were prioritised due to their broad uptake across the eDNA community. At the same time, the FAIRe metadata checklist was included as an emerging framework gaining adoption for FAIR-aligned and harmonised eDNA metadata reporting (Takahashi et al., 2025). These datasets spanned metabarcoding to metagenomics and included a variety of sequencing platforms (please see eDNAqua-Plan D4.1 for more details, Derycke et al., 2025). The main goal was to assess how users evaluate the utility of these metadata fields and to identify potential gaps. To this end, a system of six codes was used to categorise the evaluation of the use cases, which were further grouped to facilitate interpretation (Table 2). Data and code to replicate the analysis are deposited on https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/D3.2-Standards_for_eDNA_repositories/tree/main/use-case-data.

Firstly, use cases were asked to report on their considered checklist whether they filled out the metadata fields upon data submission (“filled”), and if not, whether they did have the information but opted not to fill in the fields, or they did not have the information because it was not collected or lost (“not filled”). In addition, use cases reported metadata fields that were not encountered during the submission process (“Not encountered”). In parallel, based on the filled metadata, use cases were also asked to report whether they agree with the requirement status (mandatory vs non-mandatory) of the different fields in the checklists. For the mandatory metadata fields, use cases either agreed they should be mandatory (“Agree”), disagreed and considered they should not be mandatory (“Disagree”) or did not consider the field relevant for their case (“NotRelevant”). For the non-mandatory fields, use cases either agreed they should not be mandatory (“Agree”), disagreed and believed the fields should be mandatory (“Disagree”), or did not consider the field relevant for their case (“NotRelevant”). Here, we analyse the use cases’ evaluation of the different metadata fields for the INSDC, OBIS, GBIF, and FAIRe checklists.

Table 2. Code system to categorise the evaluation of the use cases of the metadata fields in each considered checklist and their categorisation for the analysis presented in this deliverable.

Code	Meaning	Category	Mandatory metadata category	Non-mandatory metadata category
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1	The term was filled during upload, and should be mandatory	Filled	Agree	Disagree
2	The term was filled during upload, and should be optional	Filled	Disagree	Agree
3	The term was not filled because it was optional, although the data was available	Not filled	NA	NA
4	The term was not filled in; although relevant, it was not measured, or the data were lost.	Not filled	NA	NA
5	The term was not filled because it is not relevant to the study	Not filled	Not relevant	Not relevant
6	The term was not encountered because it was not included in the checklist used	Not encountered	NA	NA

3.3.1 International Sequence Database Consortium (INSDC) repository

Regarding INSDC, six partners provided input for six checklists (ENA default sample checklist, GSC MlxS sediment, GSC MlxS water, ENA Micro B3, ENA Tara Oceans, and GSC MlxS miscellaneous natural or artificial environment), totalling 550 metadata terms (see Supplementary Figures 1-4) for an overview of assessed checklists and use case reports. None of the partners used the ENA Micro B3 nor the Tara Oceans checklists, so no input was provided for these, and they were therefore excluded from our analysis. The metagenomics bacteria/archaea use case reported the highest proportion of filled metadata fields, whereas use cases relying on short-reads metabarcoding data faced the highest proportion of “Not encountered” metadata fields (Figure 4.A). Across all checklists assessed, partners agreed that the large majority of mandatory fields should retain their mandatory status (Figure 4.B). Overall, approximately 70% of the non-mandatory fields were deemed “Not relevant” by the use cases, and seven metadata fields were unanimously agreed to retain their optional status (Figure 4.C).

For the GSC MlxS “miscellaneous natural or artificial environment” checklist, only one partner selected it during their submission process. For mandatory terms, the partner agreed to retain their mandatory status. For non-mandatory terms, although the partner had collected the relevant information, none were filled in because they were optional (Supplementary Figure 1).

For the GSC MlxS “sediment” and “water” checklist, two use cases (metabarcoding long-read Nanopore fish and metagenomics bacteria/archaea) provided feedback. For most optional terms, metadata was considered “Not relevant”. However, some non-mandatory terms, such as PCR primers, sample collection device and method, or sample storage temperature, were deemed important enough in one use case to warrant designation as mandatory. Notwithstanding, these terms may not apply to all aquatic eDNA protocols (see Supplementary Figures 2 and 3). For instance, metagenomics protocols do not target any marker; thus, PCR is not used, making these fields irrelevant in these contexts.

Six partners contributed to the INSDC “default sample” checklist. For most of the 28 non-mandatory terms, metadata were either left unfilled despite being collected or considered “Not relevant”. The latter appears to be linked to the complex nature of samples, such as aquatic eDNA or bulk environmental samples, for which many metadata terms are better suited to single-organism or non-environmental samples. One of the metabarcoding short-reads invertebrates use cases suggested that the tissue_type field should be mandatory, but this was considered “Not relevant” by

the other use cases, whose samples derived from complex environmental samples. Additionally, one use case indicated that three optional terms (geographic location, isolation source, and latitude/longitude) should be mandatory (see Supplementary Figures 4). However, geographic coordinates information may also fall within the CARE principles (Carroll et al., 2023), preventing its submission to public repositories. Although most other partners had collected the relevant information, they did not submit it, as these fields were not required. One partner also reported difficulties in converting their coordinate system to the platform's expected format and gave up due to time constraints.

Figure 4. Summary of metadata completion and its utility per case study for the INSDC checklists using the categories described in Table 2. In panel A, statuses reflect whether metadata was not encountered, filled or not filled. For metadata fields that were filled, agreement with the current INSDC checklist requirement is summarised for mandatory fields (panel B) and non-mandatory metadata fields (panel C), showing the combinations of agreement, disagreement, and 'not relevant' across metadata fields. The bar height represents the number of metadata fields for a given combination of replies, and dot matrices indicate combinations of agreement types. In contrast, set sizes shown on the left indicate the total number of metadata fields associated with each agreement category.

3.3.2 Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) repository

Regarding the GBIF repository, three partners assessed two checklists, totalling 70 metadata terms. Use cases reported to have filled between 40 and 65 % of the metadata fields (Figure 5.A). All partners agreed that the mandatory terms should remain mandatory, with the only exception being `annealingTemp`, which one use case considered should be optional and was regarded as “Not relevant” by another use case (Figure 5B, but see Supplementary Figures 5 and 6). This contradictory assessment for the `annealingTemp` field derives from the different protocols used, as the metagenomics protocol does not include a PCR step. Six recommended or highly recommended (i.e., non-mandatory) metadata fields were proposed for mandatory status. Among these, `DNA_sequence`, `decimalLatitude`, and `decimalLongitude` were identified as mandatory across all three use cases. Metadata fields describing sampling environment conditions and providing SOPs were considered mandatory in two use cases. In contrast, the third recommended retaining their optional status (Figure 5C, but see Supplementary Figures 5 and 6).

As before, most non-mandatory fields should remain optional, and for some metadata fields, although the use cases possessed the requested information, it was not uploaded. Notably, more than half of the metadata fields in the GBIF and OBIS's DNA-derived data extension were not relevant to the metagenomics bacteria/archaea use case, highlighting the need for metadata fields tailored to other eDNA-based protocols beyond metabarcoding or qPCR.

Figure 5. Summary of metadata completion and its utility per case study for the GBIF checklists using the categories described in Table 2. In panel A, statuses reflect whether metadata was not encountered, filled or not filled. For metadata fields that were filled, agreement with the current GBIF checklist requirement is summarised for mandatory fields (panel B) and non-mandatory metadata fields (panel C), showing the combinations of agreement, disagreement, and 'not relevant' across metadata fields. The bar height represents the number of metadata fields for a given combination of replies, and dot matrices indicate combinations of agreement types. In contrast, set sizes shown on the left indicate the total number of metadata fields associated with each agreement category.

3.3.3 Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) repository

For the OBIS repository, two use cases assessed 31 metadata fields, with at least 50% of these fields filled during submission (Figure 6A; see Supplementary Figures 7 and 8). As in other repositories, mandatory metadata fields were considered adequate and should keep their status (Figure 6.B). Regarding non-mandatory metadata fields, none were considered to have their status raised to mandatory by the use cases. However, for four non-mandatory fields, one use case considered them mandatory. In contrast, other use cases considered them irrelevant, further highlighting the differences between protocols and potential sampling sources (Figure 6.C; see Supplementary Figures 7 and 8).

OBIS

Figure 6. Summary of metadata completion and their utility per case study for the OBIS checklists using the categories described in Table 2. In panel A, statuses reflect whether metadata was not encountered, filled or not filled. For metadata fields that were filled, agreement with the current OBIS checklist requirement is summarised for mandatory fields (panel B) and non-mandatory metadata fields (panel C), showing the combinations of agreement, disagreement, and 'not relevant' across metadata fields. The bar height represents the number of metadata fields for a given combination of replies, and dot matrices indicate combinations of agreement types. In contrast, set sizes shown on the left indicate the total number of metadata fields associated with each agreement category.

3.3.4 FAIR eDNA (FAIRe) Metadata checklist

Lastly, 337 metadata fields of the FAIRe checklist were assessed through seven use cases. The percentage of filled metadata fields varied between 7% and 50% (Figure 7.A). Among the filled mandatory metadata fields, only decimalLongitude, decimalLatitude, and evenDate were consistently considered by the use cases to retain their mandatory status. No metadata field was solely identified as needing to be optional. For the remaining mandatory fields, there was a disagreement with their current mandatory status and assessments of irrelevance by some use cases. This was particularly evident for eleven metadata fields, all belonging to the “Targeted assay detection” section (Figure 7.B; see Supplementary Figures 9-22). However, this is expected as none of the use cases relied on targeted assays, such as qPCR. For the non-mandatory metadata fields, the majority received mixed reviews, reflecting a combination of agreement, disagreement, and “Not relevant”. Additionally, 87 of the non-mandatory fields were considered “Not relevant” across the use cases. These fields were distributed across multiple FAIRe sections, including “Environment” and “Targeted assay detection” (Figure 7C, see Supplementary Figures 9-22). Furthermore, this checklist was created with metabarcoding and qPCR approaches in mind, and thus is not inclusive of metagenomics approaches.

Figure 7. Summary of metadata completion and its utility per case study for the FAIRe checklists using the categories described in Table 2. In panel A, statuses reflect whether metadata was not encountered, filled or not filled. For metadata fields that were filled, agreement with the current FAIRe checklist requirement is summarised for mandatory fields (panel B) and non-mandatory metadata fields (panel C), showing the combinations of agreement, disagreement, and 'not relevant' across metadata fields. The bar height represents the number of metadata fields for a given combination of replies, and dot matrices indicate combinations of agreement types. In contrast, set sizes shown on the left indicate the total number of metadata fields associated with each agreement category.

Overall, the use cases were congruent across all checklists, recommending that the mandatory terms retain their mandatory status. Many of the optional terms, however, were left blank, even though the use cases included that information. These fields are often considered time-consuming, and as they are not mandatory, they are easily left empty during data submission.

4. Data Mapping

4.1. Introduction to Metadata Alignment Models

As we have seen throughout this report, eDNA metadata is often fragmented across different workflow stages, stored in multiple locations, and described using heterogeneous standards as organisations adopt standards that best fit their immediate needs, often misaligned with eDNA-specific requirements. This fragmentation and lack of harmonisation hinder data reuse, limit interoperability, and ultimately slow large-scale analyses and scientific progress by making (meta)data incomparable. The primary objective of this task was to develop alignment models that harmonise existing metadata standards, establishing a foundation for improved interoperability of eDNA data (Figure 8). These models are necessary because users inconsistently interpret metadata terms, and equivalent concepts are represented differently across checklists and schemas. Addressing these issues is essential for enabling consistent metadata interpretation and cross-platform integration.

Figure 8. Simplified conceptual diagram of fragmented community data standards and illustrative mappings for alignment. Actual stakeholder-to-schema relationships are many-to-many and more complex than depicted.

Ideally, all metadata within a domain would conform to a single standard, and similarly for all relevant data. Such would make data integration and computational queries facile. However, as demonstrated in WP2’s D2.2 (Woollard et al., 2025) and WP3’s M7 (Boulanger et al., 2025) reports, this remains far from reality. Such fragmentation is common across life sciences and beyond, but pragmatic solutions exist.

A decade ago, DwC core terms and GSC MlxS core terms were mapped. This effort resulted in the MlxS-DwC extension, which enabled the integration of MlxS core terms into DwC-compliant metadata, and in a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between TDWG and GSC (Meyer et al., 2023). This MoU created formal, cooperative alignment between organisations that would otherwise develop standards independently, reducing duplication of effort, improving interoperability through harmonised terminology and values, and reassuring stakeholders of ongoing compatibility.

To address interoperability challenges in eDNA metadata reporting, we adopted the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM), building upon the practices established in the earlier DwC and MlxS alignment effort. This good practice pattern is to map conceptually similar terms from common standards, enabling metadata in repositories following different standards to be more easily interoperable (Figure 9; Matentzoglou et al., 2022). Its simple spreadsheet format facilitates and supports broad adoption while promoting the reuse of established mappings across different contexts. SSSOM enables mappings to be described with explicit semantic relationships, supported by clear justification, confidence, and provenance information. When implemented in accordance with its 5-Star Entity Mappings, which aim to increase reusability and transparency in Open Science mappings, this shared structure explains mapping decisions, supports consistent interpretation, builds trust, and facilitates conflict resolution across use cases (Matentzoglou et al., 2022).

Figure 9. Conceptual diagram of a standard alignment model using the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM) framework. The figure shows how a term from the GBIF/OBIS’s DNA-derived extension (samp_name) is aligned to a corresponding term in the Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence (MIxS) (MIXS:0001107, sample name) via the predicate exactMatch from the Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) vocabulary. The alignment includes subject and object identifiers and labels, as well as associated mapping metadata (mapping date, confidence, and justification), shown within the dotted box.

This deliverable covers the development of semantic and syntactic mappings. The semantic mapping aims to capture differences in the meaning of terms by comparing term names and their descriptions. In contrast, the syntactic mapping model focuses on differences in the values, expressions and structural rules associated with metadata terms that have already been semantically mapped. Table 3 illustrates this distinction. The concept ‘habitat’ refers to the natural home of an organism, whereas ‘environment type’ describes the primary or adjacent environmental system from which the specimen was collected. Although related, these concepts differ semantically and therefore represent distinct meanings. With respect to syntax, values such as ‘20°C’, ‘293.15K’, and ‘68°F’ all represent the same concept, temperature, but are expressed using different units. Consequently, while they represent the same physical quantity, they are not directly comparable as numeric values without prior syntactic normalisation. The differences between semantic and syntactic alignment models are discussed in more detail in Section 4.3.

Table 3. Semantic and syntactic mismatches.

	Semantic	Syntactic
Concept	Mismatch in meaning	Mismatch in format/convention
Example	‘habitat’ vs. ‘environment type’	‘20°C’ vs ‘293.15K’ vs ‘68°F’

4.2. Mapping Approach

We initiated the mapping effort with the GBIF/OBIS’s DNA-derived data checklist (version 1, released in 2023-09-18) (https://rs.gbif.org/extension/gbif/1.0/dna_derived_data_2024-07-11.xml) against version 6.2.0 of MIxS, and, for a single case, version <http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/doc/list/2023-09-18> of DwC.

To establish the alignment models, we followed the mapping approach described in the ‘Aligning Standards Communities for Omics Biodiversity Data: Sustainable Darwin Core-MIxS

Interoperability' manuscript (Meyer et al., 2023), to maintain continuity with previously developed eDNA mappings while adapting the approach where necessary. To maintain a comparable SSSOM structure, we adopted the semantic and syntactic mapping framework from that work, resulting in two tables, one for semantic mappings and one for syntactic mappings, that together form a single mapping set.

The mapping set meets SSSOM's minimal metadata requirements. As the SSSOM documentation has been updated since the previous DwC-MIxS mapping effort, we included the newly mandatory *mapping_justification* property, which was not required at the time of the earlier work. For syntactic mapping, additional non-standard slots (*ext_syntax_predicate_id*, *ext_syntax_comment*) were added, consistent with prior DwC-MIxS syntactic alignment practices. These slots were defined in accordance with SSSOM specifications using the 'ext_' prefix for slot names and the '<http://sssom.invalid/>' prefix for the CURIE map namespace (Matentzoglou et al., 2022). In addition to the semantic and syntactic mappings, the DwC-MIxS mapping set included a separate support mapping. This mapping captures both semantic and syntactic elements in a single table, including definitions and the expected value syntax for both object and subject. Our mapping set does not include this secondary output, as it was a DwC-MIxS internal task force working document.

Semantic and syntactic relationships were expressed using the Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) vocabulary, primarily through the sub-properties *skos:exactMatch*, *skos:broadMatch* and *skos:relatedMatch* (Miles et al., 2009). The overall matching process was documented using the Semantic Mapping Vocabulary (Matentzoglou et al., 2022). As the mappings were produced exclusively through manual expert curation, all *mapping_justification* fields were populated as *semapv:ManualMappingCuration*.

Semantic mapping was performed as the first step. This process involved manually assessing metadata term labels and definitions across the selected checklists to infer semantic relationships between terms. Mapping decisions were based on a close reading of term names and descriptions. *skos:exactMatch* was assigned when term names and definitions were closely aligned. *skos:broadMatch* was used when the subject term was more specific than the object term, with the object term encompassing the subject term. Any mapping considerations that could not be adequately captured through SKOS predicates alone were documented as comments (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Overview of the methodological approach taken to conduct the mapping effort. Panel A depicts the overall mapping framework, while Panels B and C show the decision flowcharts for semantic and syntactic alignment, respectively.

Syntactic mapping was subsequently conducted only for those term pairs for which a semantic relationship had already been established. No additional syntactic mappings were created independently. *skos:exactMatch* was assigned when value structure, formatting, and patterns were identical and no syntactic normalisation was required. Whereas *skos:relatedMatch* was applied when the syntactic scope was similar, but value representations differed (e.g., integer versus float), indicating the need for normalisation. *skos:broadMatch* was used when the subject term expected a more constrained value than the object term, such as a single identifier compared to a label-identifier pair. In both of these latter cases, syntactic normalisation is required.

For mappings where no correspondence with MlxS could be identified, or where confidence in the mapping was very low, no predicate was assigned. This approach reduces overall mapping coverage; however, in accordance with SSSOM recommendations, mappings should be transparently documented as inaccurate, incomplete, imprecise, or conflicting. In this context, imprecision is not inherently problematic, provided it is explicitly documented; undocumented or implicit imprecision undermines the interpretability and reuse of the mappings (Matentzoglou et al., 2022).

BOLD is the largest repository of reference barcode information for its target taxonomies and is thus important to be able to interoperate this with the wider ecosystem. It uses its own Barcode Core Data Model¹⁰ (BCDM) rather than an external standard, and initial mappings between BCDM and GSC MlxS were performed at the BGE hackathon in 2024¹¹. We used this as a starting point and improved these further. This allows us to demonstrate interoperability across reference libraries, sequence/sample data, and observational data.

In collaboration with the Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) project (<https://biodiversitygenomics.eu/>), we extended the mapping effort to include an alignment between the Barcode Core Data Model (BCDM) and MlxS Core.

The BCDM-MlxS alignment followed the methodology described above (Figure 10) and was initiated using a support mapping file. As described above, our first mapping effort between the DNA-derived extension and MlxS did not include a support mapping. For the BCDM-MlxS alignment, however, we agreed that enabling simultaneous semantic and syntactic mapping would improve efficiency. A single combined mapping was created first, capturing both semantic and syntactic elements. Separate semantic and syntactic mapping files were then derived from this unified file.

The mapping followed the same structural conventions as the DwC-MlxS alignment, including explicit subject and object definitions, value syntax, and format specifications. We found this combined support file to be more comprehensive and easier to collaborate on, as all mapping information was consolidated into a single place. Nevertheless, because this approach does not fully align with standard SSSOM practice, the separate semantic and syntactic files were subsequently generated in accordance with recommended standards. The alignment used the BCDM release from November 2025 and MlxS version 6.2.0.

4.3. Alignment Models

4.3.1. GBIF/OBIS's DNA-Derived extension and the MlxS Alignment Model

The mapping effort produced 99 semantic mappings and 87 syntactic mappings, addressing all 123 terms in the DNA-derived data extension. Each term was treated as a subject in the mapping

¹⁰ https://github.com/DNAdiversity/BCDM/blob/main/field_definitions.tsv

¹¹ <https://github.com/douglove/BGE-Barcoding-Hackathon-Report>

process, resulting in approximately 81% semantic and 71% syntactic coverage. No duplicate mappings were generated; every term was mapped exactly once.

For semantic mappings, 78.9% (97 terms) were exact matches, 1.6% (2 terms) were broad matches, and 19.5% (24 terms) were unmapped. Syntactically, 69.1% (85 terms) were exact matches, 2.44% (3 terms) were broad matches, and 1.6% (2 terms) were related matches, with 26.8% (33 terms) unmappable. Unmapped terms are still included in the mapping file; however, they have no associated predicate identifier.

The standards mapped to the DNA-derived checklist were treated as objects. MlxS served as the primary target standard. When no equivalent MlxS term could be identified, terms were instead mapped to their originating standard to assess whether their definitions or syntax had changed during integration into the DNA-derived data extension. As a result, 93 terms were mapped to MlxS (75.6%), 1 to Darwin Core (0.8%), 5 to Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN; 4.1%), and 24 terms remained unmapped (19.5%). Additionally, because the terms in the DNA-derived checklist lacked explicit numerical identifiers or entirely written field names, being provided only as abbreviations, the `subject_id` and `subject_label` fields were kept highly similar.

The mapping files for the DNA-derived extension and MIXS Core alignment model can be retrieved at <https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/dwc-mixs-edna-derived-extension/tree/e-dna-derived-extension>.

Semantic Mapping

Semantically, we found that the meanings of all terms were highly similar, if not identical, to the corresponding terms in the MlxS checklist, except for two terms: *pcr_primer_forward* and *pcr_primer_reverse*. These terms showed a narrower correspondence with the MlxS term *pcr_primers*. While the DNA-derived data extension expects the sequence of each primer to be provided separately (i.e. forward and reverse primers represented as distinct terms), MlxS expects both primers to be reported together within a single, aggregated field (broader). A subsample of the semantic alignment model, containing only the first six columns, is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Examples of semantic mappings between the GBIF/OBIS DNA-Derived extension and the MlxS standard, represented using the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM). Not all minimal metadata elements are included.

subject_id	subject_label	predicate_id	object_id	object_label
dnaextension:samp_name	samp_name	skos:exactMatch	MIXS:0001107	sample name
dnaextension:pcr_primer_forward	pcr_primer_forward	skos:broadMatch	MIXS:0000046	pcr primers
dnaextension:pcr_primer_reverse	pcr_primer_reverse	skos:broadMatch	MIXS:0000046	pcr primers

In total, 24 terms from the DNA-derived data extension could not be mapped to MlxS. Of these, 20 were derived from the MIQE (Minimum Information for Publication of Quantitative Real-Time PCR Experiments) guidelines. With no provenance information describing how the DNA-derived terms were derived from the MIQE guidelines, it was difficult to infer semantic correspondence. The remaining four terms (*pcr_primer_name_forward*, *pcr_primer_name_reverse*, *pcr_primer_reference*,

and *DNA_sequence*) are original to the DNA-derived data extension, and no equivalent terms were identified in MlxS.

The complete semantic alignment model can be found at https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/dwc-mixs-edna-derived-extension/blob/e-dna-derived-extension/e-dna-derived-extension/mapping/e-dna-derived-extension_mappingSemantic-2.0.0.sssom.tsv.

Syntactic mapping

Syntactic misalignments were observed only for terms adopted from MlxS. In contrast, terms adopted from the GGBN and DwC remained exact matches, indicating that the expected syntax was not modified from the originating standards.

For example, the expected value formatting for the MlxS term *specific_host* is ‘Homo sapiens, 9606’, whereas the DNA-derived extension expects only the identifier ‘9606’. As such, the predicate *skos:broadMatch* was applied to this mapping, as the subject term expected a single identifier rather than a label-identifier pair, and therefore returned a more constrained value than the object term. On the contrary, the term *samp_taxon_id* in both MlxS and the DNA-derived extension expected identical value formatting: a text string followed by a space and an NCBI Taxonomy identifier enclosed in square brackets, with no additional characters before or after (e.g. ‘Gut Metagenome [NCBITaxon:749906]’). Consequently, the predicate *skos:exactMatch* was assigned (Table 5).

Table 5. Examples of syntactic mappings between the GBIF/OBIS DNA-Derived extension and the MlxS standard, represented according to the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM). Not all minimal metadata elements are included.

subject_id	ext_syntax_predicate_id	object_id	object_label
dnaextension:specific_host	skos:broadMatch	MIXS:0000029	host scientific name
dnaextension:samp_taxon_id	skos:exactMatch	MIXS:0001320	taxonomy ID of DNA sample
dnaextension:seq_meth	skos:relatedMatch	MIXS:0000050	sequencing method
dnaextension:contam_score	skos:relatedMatch	MIXS:0000072	contamination score
dnaextension:pcr_primer_forward	skos:broadMatch	MIXS:0000046	pcr primers
dnaextension:pcr_primer_reverse	skos:broadMatch	MIXS:0000046	pcr primers

For PCR primer-related terms, the DNA-derived extension adopts a narrower concept, separating forward and reverse primers into separate fields (*pcr_primer_forward* and *pcr_primer_reverse*), in contrast to the single *pcr_primers* in MlxS. Consequently, the predicate was assigned as *skos:broadMatch*, as the object, MlxS term (*pcr_primers*), encompasses a broader syntax than the corresponding terms in the DNA-derived extension, subject. Specifically, the DNA-derived extension expects a single nucleotide sequence per field. In contrast, MlxS defines a structured regular expression requiring both forward and reverse primer sequences to be provided within a single field, each prefixed by an identifier (e.g. ‘FWD:’ and ‘REV:’) and separated by a delimiter.

Some terms were left syntactically unmapped due to misaligned or ambiguous specifications. For example, *samp_collec_device* and *samp_collec_method* could not be confidently mapped.

For *samp_collec_device*, the example provided in the DNA-derived extension appears to be duplicated from *samp_collec_method*, which hinders inference of the expected value formatting. Moreover, the DNA-derived extension does not specify any structured syntax for values. Both MlxS and the DNA-derived data extension describe *samp_collec_device* as accepting terms from the Genomic Epidemiology Ontology under 'specimen collection device'; however, this term has been deprecated (https://ontobee.org/ontology/GENEPIO?iri=http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/GENEPIO_0002094) in favour of the OBI vocabulary. Despite identical descriptions, the definitions are therefore both outdated and ambiguous, increasing the likelihood of divergent, non-comparable value syntax across users.

For *samp_collec_method*, the example provided in the DNA-derived data extension does not align with the structured pattern described in MlxS. Due to these inconsistencies and ambiguities, we had low confidence in assigning predicates for these terms.

The complete syntactic alignment model can be found at https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/dwc-mixs-edna-derived-extension/blob/e-dna-derived-extension/e-dna-derived-extension/mapping/e-dna-derived-extension_mappingSyntactic-2.0.0.sssom.tsv.

4.3.2. Barcode Core Data Model and MlxS Core Alignment Model

The mapping effort produced 35 semantic mappings and 34 syntactic mappings, addressing all 83 terms in the BCDM. Each term was treated as a subject in the mapping process, resulting in approximately 42% and 41% semantic and syntactic coverage, respectively. No duplicate mappings were generated; every term was mapped exactly once.

For semantic mappings, 13.3% (11 terms) were narrow matches, 12% (10 terms) were close matches, 9.6% (8 terms) were related matches, 6.0% (5 terms) were broad matches, and 1.2% (1 term) were exact matches, leaving 57.8% (48 terms) unmapped. Syntactically, 6.0% (5 terms) were close matches, 15.7% (13 terms) were narrow matches, and 19.3% (16 terms) were related matches, with 59% (49 terms) unmapped. Unmapped terms are still included in the mapping file; however, they have no associated predicate identifier.

Similar to the previous alignment model, the fields in the BCDM lacked explicit numerical identifiers or fully written field names, being provided only as abbreviations; as such, the `subject_id` and `subject_label` fields were kept highly similar.

The mapping files for the Barcode Core Data Model and MlxS Core alignment model can be retrieved at https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/BCDM-MlxS_SSSOM_mappings/tree/main/BCDM_MlxS_SSSOM_mappings.

Semantic Mapping

For the BCDM alignment effort, semantic misalignments were widespread. As described above, exact matches were rare (1 term), and most associations exhibited some degree of semantic divergence. Table 6 presents one example of each type of association identified between the two resources.

Table 6. Examples of semantic mappings between the Barcode Core Data Model (BCDM) and the MixS Core standard, represented following the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM). Not all minimal metadata elements are included.

subject_id	predicate_id	object_id	object_label
bcdm:inst	skos:exactMatch	MIXS:0001152	MIXS:repository_name
bcdm:marker_code	skos:closeMatch	MIXS:0000044	MIXS:target_gene
bcdm:specimen_linkout	skos:relatedMatch	MIXS:0000091	MIXS:associated_resource
bcdm:collection_time	skos:narrowMatch	MIXS:0000011	MIXS:collection_date
bcdm:life_stage	skos:broadMatch	MIXS:0000251	MIXS:host_life_stage

The exact match between *bcdm:inst* and *MIXS:repository_name* illustrates this: although the field names and definitions differ, their meanings can be inferred to be exact equivalences based on the definitions “Institution storing the physical specimen” and “The name of the institution where the sample or DNA extract is held (...)”, respectively.

A mapping that is not an exact equivalence but is similar enough to be considered interchangeable is assigned *skos:closeMatch*. One example of this is the mapping between *bcdm:marker_code* and *MIXS:target_gene*, as a “Short code associated with the sequenced marker(gene)” (BCDM) can be considered as the “Targeted gene (...) for marker gene studies” (MixS).

A *skos:relatedMatch* is intended to assert an associative link between two concepts that are meaningfully connected but not interchangeable. In this case, *bcdm:specimen_linkout* is related to *MIXS:associated_resource* because both properties describe references to external resources linked to a specimen or sequence record.

However, they were not assigned a *skos:closeMatch* because their semantics, scope, and intended usage do not sufficiently align to support near-equivalence. *bcdm:specimen_linkout* is defined as “a link to an external resource for the specimen record,” emphasising a specimen-centric approach to documentation and curation. In contrast, *MixS:associated_resource* is defined as “a related resource that is referenced, cited, or otherwise associated with the sequence,” which is broader, sequence-centric, and includes a wider range of associations (e.g., publications, datasets, protocols) that may not directly describe the specimen itself. As a result, substituting one term for the other risks semantic drift and a loss of contextual precision.

bcdm:collection_time has a narrower semantic scope than *MixS:collection_date*. In *MixS*, *collection_date* is intended to capture the full temporal description of the collection event, typically including both the calendar date and the time. In contrast, *bcdm:collection_time* represents only the time component of that event. Because the meaning of *bcdm:collection_time* is fully contained within but does not, by itself, capture the meaning of *MixS:collection_date*, the relationship between the two terms is best expressed as a *skos:narrowMatch*, with *MixS:collection_date* representing the broader concept.

In contrast, *bcdm:life_stage* has a broader semantic scope than *MixS:host_life_stage*. While both terms describe a life stage, *MixS:host_life_stage* is explicitly limited to the host organism, whereas *bcdm:life_stage* does not impose this restriction. As such, the BCDM term is broader.

Syntactic Mapping

Similar to the semantic mappings, and consequently, semantic misalignments were also widespread. Here, neither exact nor broad matches were established, with most associations

exhibiting significant syntactic divergence. Table 7 presents one example of each type of association identified between the two resources.

Table 7. Examples of syntactic mappings between the Barcode Core Data Model (BCDM) and the MixS Core standard, represented according to the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM). Not all minimal metadata elements are included.

subject_id	ext_syntax_predicate_id	object_id	object_label
bcdm:coord	skos:closeMatch	MIXS:0000009	MIXS:lat_lon
bcdm:sampling_protocol	skos:relatedMatch	MIXS:0001225	MIXS:samp_collect_method
bcdm:identification_method	skos:narrowMatch	MIXS:0000064	MIXS:tax_class
bcdm:identification_rank	skos:narrowMatch	MIXS:0000064	MIXS:tax_class

The closest syntactic association assigned was `skos:closeMatch`, applied when the expected value's formatting and structure were considered near-equivalent. For example, `bcdm:coord` and `MIXS:lat_lon` both represent latitude and longitude in degrees. Syntactically, the object (`MIXS:lat_lon`) requires a structured pattern (`^{lat} {lon}$`), which closely aligns with the subject (`bcdm:coord`). However, the subject does not provide an explicit example of this structure, as its expected format is an array, rather than a fixed string.

A `skos:relatedMatch` was assigned when both fields capture the same type of information, but their expected syntactic patterns differ substantially. This association holds for `bcdm:sampling_protocol` and `MIXS:samp_collect_method`. Both properties describe the methods used to collect a sample. However, the subject (`bcdm:sampling_protocol`) allows names, references, or textual descriptions of the collection method, while the object (`MIXS:samp_collect_method`) expects a more structured format (`^{PMID}{DOI}{URL}{text}$`). Because the two terms convey related information but impose different syntactic constraints, their association is best captured as `skos:relatedMatch` rather than a closer equivalence. This relationship was the most commonly assigned mapping property (19.3%).

`skos:narrowMatch` was the second-most-common property. It was assigned when the values of the subject (BCDM) were fully contained within, but did not fully capture, the broader value of the object (MixS). For example, `bcdm:identification_method` and `bcdm:identification_rank` were mapped to `MIXS:tax_class`. The BCDM properties describe, respectively, the method used for taxonomic classification and the classification rank in isolation, whereas the MixS property combines these with references and thresholds. Neither checklist imposes a strict, structured pattern. Because the subject holds a narrower portion of the object's broader syntax, the mapping was expressed as `skos:narrowMatch`.

4.4. Identified Misalignments

GBIF/OBIS's DNA-Derived extension and the MixS standard Alignment Model

Our main finding from the mapping was the presence of syntactic mismatches related to checklist versioning, as previously illustrated in Table 5. The metadata terms derived from the MixS core, as presented in the DNA-derived data extension, were based on earlier versions of the MixS core. With MixS version 6 already released and version 7 soon to follow, we expect these incongruities

to worsen and increasingly negatively impact dataset aggregation, metadata field mapping, and consistent annotation across studies (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Syntactic mismatches were found due to versioning inconsistencies in the expected formatting for the *tax_ident* term between version 1.0 of the GBIF/OBIS's DNA-derived extension and V6.0 of MixS.

Another key inconsistency was the presence of terms with unknown provenance. From the 123 terms detailed in the DNA-derived extension, 20 were derived from the MIQE guidelines. Established in 2009, the MIQE guidelines serve as a checklist specifying the minimum information that should be reported for methods employing quantitative PCR (qPCR; Bustin 2009). As such, the MIQE guidelines do not define metadata terms. When these specifications were integrated into the DNA-derived data checklist, the rationale for the transformation process that generated metadata terms from the guideline specifications was not documented. Our efforts to infer these relationships through manual comparison of MIQE checklist items and DNA-derived terms revealed that the connections are non-obvious (Figure 12). Additionally, the MIQE guidelines have since been updated to reflect recent advances in qPCR technology (Bustin 2025), further complicating users' and developers' ability to infer relationships and provenance.

A.		B.	
<p>annealingTemp</p> <p>en: The reaction temperature during the annealing phase of PCR.</p> <p>Examples: 60</p> <p>Qualname http://rs.gbif.org/terms/miqe/annealingTemp</p> <p>Namespace http://rs.gbif.org/terms/miqe/</p> <p>Group nucleic acid sequence source</p> <p>Data Type decimal</p> <p>Required false</p>		<p>qPCR target information</p> <p>If multiplex, efficiency and LOD of each assay E</p> <p>Sequence accession number E</p> <p>Location of amplicon D</p> <p>Amplicon length E</p> <p>In silico specificity screen (BLAST, etc) E</p> <p>Pseudogenes, retropseudogenes or other homologs? D</p> <p>Sequence alignment D</p> <p>Secondary structure analysis of amplicon D</p> <p>Location of each primer by exon or intron (if applicable) E</p> <p>What splice variants are targeted? E</p>	
<p>annealingTempUnit</p> <p>en: Measurement unit of the reaction temperature during the annealing phase of PCR.</p> <p>Examples: Degrees celsius</p> <p>Qualname http://rs.gbif.org/terms/miqe/annealingTempUnit</p> <p>Namespace http://rs.gbif.org/terms/miqe/</p> <p>Group nucleic acid sequence source</p> <p>Data Type</p> <p>Required false</p>		<p>qPCR oligonucleotides</p> <p>Primer sequences E</p> <p>RTPrimerDB identification number D</p> <p>Probe sequences D**</p> <p>Location and identity of any modifications E</p> <p>Manufacturer of oligonucleotides D</p> <p>Purification method D</p>	
<p>probeReporter</p> <p>en: Type of fluorophore (reporter) used. Probe anneals within amplified target DNA. Polymerase activity degrades the probe that has annealed to the template, and the probe releases the fluorophore from it and breaks the proximity to the quencher, thus allowing fluorescence of the fluorophore.</p> <p>Examples: FAM</p> <p>Qualname http://rs.gbif.org/terms/miqe/probeReporter</p> <p>Namespace http://rs.gbif.org/terms/miqe/</p> <p>Group nucleic acid sequence source</p> <p>Data Type</p> <p>Required false</p>		<p>qPCR protocol</p> <p>Complete reaction conditions E</p> <p>Reaction volume and amount of cDNA/DNA E</p> <p>Primer, (probe), Mg++ and dNTP concentrations E</p> <p>Polymerase identity and concentration E</p> <p>Buffer/kit identity and manufacturer E</p> <p>Exact chemical constitution of the buffer D</p> <p>Additives (SYBR Green I, DMSO, etc.) E</p> <p>Manufacturer of plates/tubes and catalog number D</p> <p>Complete thermocycling parameters E</p> <p>Reaction setup (manual/robotic) D</p> <p>Manufacturer of qPCR instrument E</p>	
<p>probeQuencher</p> <p>en: Type of quencher used. The quencher molecule quenches the fluorescence emitted by the fluorophore when excited by the cyclers light source As long as fluorophore and the quencher are in proximity, quenching inhibits any fluorescence signals.</p> <p>Examples: NFQ-MGB</p> <p>Qualname http://rs.gbif.org/terms/miqe/probeQuencher</p> <p>Namespace http://rs.gbif.org/terms/miqe/</p> <p>Group nucleic acid sequence source</p> <p>Data Type</p> <p>Required false</p>		<p>qPCR validation</p>	

Figure 12. Subsample of MIQE-derived terms (Minimum Information for Publication of Quantitative Real-Time PCR Experiments, <https://rdml.org/miqe.html>) in the GBIF/OBIS’s DNA-derived extension (https://rs.gbif.org/extension/gbif/1.0/dna_derived_data_2024-07-11.xml), illustrating that relationships between the resulting DNA-derived metadata terms (panel A) and the original MIQE checklist items (panel B) are not readily inferable from the extension itself.

We also note that the DNA-derived checklist does not specify the expected value syntax for its constituent terms. As a result, users must rely solely on the provided examples to infer the required formatting when submitting values. This lack of explicit guidance can lead to confusion and hinder comparability, as different users may adopt divergent value structures that cannot be consistently captured or validated with a single regular expression. This issue is further exacerbated when examples are incorrect; for instance, as previously noted, the example provided for *samp_collec_device* corresponds instead to *samp_collec_method*.

Barcode Core Data Model and MIxS Core Alignment Model

For the mappings between BCDM and MIxS Core, the 48 unmapped terms do not reflect gaps in documentation or provenance. Instead, most result from differences in repository scope and underlying infrastructure design. BCDM includes terms specific to the biodiversity domain that fall outside MIxS’s focus on sequence data, and therefore, these terms naturally lack counterparts. This shows that the reduced mapping coverage is a consequence of inherent differences in the purpose and domain focus of each checklist, rather than shortcomings in the mapping process itself.

The same applies to the mappings that were successfully established: based on our analysis, any differences were not primarily due to checklist version mismatches, but rather to variations in term definitions and syntax implementations.

4.5. Critical Requirements for Future Mappings

Throughout the mapping process, we identified three critical requirements for future mapping efforts. First, mapping provenance should be systematically recorded. As previously detailed, provenance is essential for building trust and ensuring transparency, particularly for follow-up revisions and updates of mapping sets. Relevant provenance information includes the mapping authors, the creation date, the versions of the standards used, and the mapping approaches and decisions applied.

Second, confidence indicators should be incorporated. Assigning confidence scores to individual mappings allows users to assess their reliability and suitability for specific use cases.

Third, hierarchical relationships between terms must be carefully ascertained. Terms are often related hierarchically rather than through exact one-to-one equivalence (Figure 13). Accurately capturing these relationships reduces information loss, preserves semantic specificity, and limits the need for downstream assumptions.

Figure 13. Illustrative example of a hierarchical relationship between concepts. Adapted from: SKOS Core Guide. W3C Working Draft 2 November 2005.

Finally, transparency is achieved not only through explicit documentation of mapping accuracy but also of the completeness of mapping coverage, including reporting known errors, community feedback, and identifying coverage gaps, missing terms, and scope limitations. Making these limitations visible allows users to assess the reliability and applicability of mappings when reusing mapped data or expanding mapping sets.

4.6. Key Outcomes and Next Steps

The mapping approach was developed in close collaboration with Pier Luigi Buttigieg, an international advisor for the eDNAqua-Plan project and a convener of the “Sustainable DarwinCore MIxS Interoperability” effort (<https://www.tdwg.org/community/gbwg/mixs/>). Our primary goal was to follow the mapping approach established in this previous alignment effort, ensuring continuity with earlier work, particularly under the previously established Memorandum of Understanding (Meyer et al., 2023), increasing visibility of both past and current initiatives, and promoting future adoption and updates. We actively engaged relevant groups to ensure our work would be useful, avoid unnecessary duplication, and advance metadata standards in the eDNA domain. To support this goal, we prioritised transparency and alignment with current community needs throughout the development of the alignment model.

GBIF/OBIS's DNA-Derived extension and the MixS standard Alignment Model

For the DNA-Derived extension and MixS Core mappings, we did this in two ways. First, we communicated our intention to develop an alignment model by opening an issue in the GitHub repository of the TDWG Genomic Biodiversity Interest Group (GBWG) (<https://github.com/tdwg/gbwg/issues/83>). This informed group members of our mapping objectives, enabled feedback or redirection where necessary, and helped ensure that the resulting model was tailored to the group's needs. Second, we created new SSSOM files for both the semantic and syntactic alignments, and uploaded them to GitHub as a new branch within the repository hosting the DwC-MixS alignment. This approach facilitates future branching, updates, and community-driven extension of the work (<https://github.com/eDNAqua-Plan-project/dwc-mixs-edna-derived-extension/tree/e-dna-derived-extension>).

While attempting to establish mappings, one of the first obstacles found was the lack of defined identifiers in the DNA-derived extension. A resolvable reference is essential for the SSSOM model, which uses the EntityReference type to establish linkages between entities in mappings. Ideally, these references are expressed as URIs (Berners-Lee 2025) or CURIEs (Birbeck 2010) to ensure they are globally unique, persistent, and resolvable. We contacted the GBIF portal team (github.com/gbif/portal-feedback/issues/5903) to request functional namespaces so we could link the sources being mapped. While a URI or a similar unique, persistent and resolvable reference was not created, the update now allows users to point directly to the term location on the extension page, helping resolve ambiguity when full URIs are not used.

After completion of the mapping set, including the semantic and syntactic alignment, the files were submitted via a pull request to the same working group one year later (<https://github.com/tdwg/gbwg/pull/84>). Alongside the submission, we documented the main findings of the mapping effort, including identified versioning misalignments and missing term provenance. We also requested that the working group review the mappings between the DNA-derived data extension and MixS Core before proceeding to broader review or endorsement within TDWG.

The lack of provenance for the MIQE-based qPCR terms was discussed directly with GBIF members via email and formally registered in GitHub discussions (<https://github.com/tdwg/gbwg/issues/83>). It was noted that assessing the actual usage of these terms would be beneficial and that, if uptake was low, their removal from the extension should be considered. In such a case, it was suggested that the terms be replaced with those from the community-oriented and increasingly adopted FAIRe checklist.

With respect to broader TDWG review and endorsement, conveners of the Darwin Core Maintenance Group provided constructive feedback on the overall structure of the mapping set, enabling further refinement. While recognising the value of the work, they also clarified that the DNA-derived extension falls outside the formal remit of TDWG standards governance, as it was developed by GBIF and OBIS and is maintained by GBIF. Consequently, the extension and its associated mappings were deemed outside the charge of the Darwin Core Maintenance Group, as defined in the MoU.

It was therefore suggested that the mappings be archived and maintained by GBIF. GBIF staff further indicated that the mapping could serve as a valuable basis for future updates to the DNA-derived extension. However, any such update would likely be discussed only after the conclusion of the 90-day public comment period for the new Darwin Core Data Packages (DwC-DP) proposal and after subsequent updates to the Darwin Core-MixS mappings under the new DwC-DP framework.

Barcode Core Data Model and MlxS Core Alignment Model

For the BCDM-MlxS alignment model, transparency and alignment with community needs were ensured through close collaboration with the BGE project and by reviewing and updating the project's previous alignment under the SSSOM framework. We used the previous alignment as a base, updating the tabular format to include SSSOM minimal metadata slots and a CURIE map. This process was carried out in a Google Sheet, allowing team feedback and building on the support mapping table adopted in the earlier DwC-MlxS mapping.

Initially, we did not recognise the full value of the support mapping table adopted in the previous DwC-MlxS mapping. We therefore did not apply it in our initial mapping effort between the DNA-derived extension and MlxS Core. The approach was later adopted when initiating the BCDM-MlxS mappings, where it proved highly effective. Simultaneously performing semantic and syntactic alignment was significantly more productive in terms of time and coordination. This structure also supports a community-based workflow, as contributors do not need to switch between multiple files. Once aligned, the semantic and syntactic fields were duplicated into separate files as required.

Once the alignments were complete, the semantic and syntactic fields were exported into separate files as required. As with our previous alignment effort, the resulting mapping set was uploaded to a fork of the BCDM repository and submitted to the working group via a pull request (<https://github.com/DNAdiversity/BCDM/pull/7>), facilitating adoption of the original resource and enabling community-driven discussion, revision, and extension.

Next Steps

Achieving high-quality mappings is challenging. Creating and maintaining these efforts requires costly expertise in domain knowledge, semantics, and technical data handling. Mappings also change frequently as data standards are updated, new releases are introduced, new technologies are adopted, and requirements evolve (Matentzoglou et al., 2022). As such, mapping efforts are dependent on a highly active and diverse team. These are scarce, and previous initiatives like the “Sustainable DarwinCore MlxS Interoperability” created to map MlxS and DwC terms (Meyer et al., 2023) are deemed inactive after the mapping effort is completed. This results in a lack of initiative continuity. A key takeaway from this effort is that the goal is not to develop isolated mappings, but to contribute to a mapping commons sustained through community collaboration to aggregate, harmonise, maintain, and share mappings and supporting tools (Figure 14) (Matentzoglou et al., 2022).

Figure 14. Recommended workflow for follow-up mapping efforts in the eDNA domain, based on the approach applied in this work.

With this goal in mind, some members of the T3.2 team joined the FAIRe taskforces to promote further collaboration and continuity. These are the ‘Environmental Samples and eDNA’ in TDWG (<https://www.tdwg.org/community/gbwg/enviro/>) and the ‘eDNA’ GSC (<https://www.gensc.org/pages/projects/eDNA-project.html>) working groups, led by Miwa Takahashi (CSIRO), the convener for the FAIRe checklist. The FAIRe project is already gaining traction within the community; as such, we believe that joining and aligning efforts with this already-proposed and

comprehensive checklist is preferable to developing novel eDNA metadata field recommendations. These task force groups aim to contribute to the development and adoption of an official metadata extension checklist tailored to eDNA needs within the two official standard bodies, TDWG and GSC, by selecting and aligning the most significant fields. We also introduced the alignment model concept to the task force, and different mapping sets were initiated to formally map the FAIRe checklist to the main deriving checklists. This collaboration culminated in the task members' participation in the Genomic Standard Consortium Annual Conference in Cambridge in the last week of August 2025, contributing to discussions on provenance recording processes during the checklist proposal phase, alignment with Minimum Information about any Ancient Sequence project (MInAS, <https://www.mixs-minas.org/>), and the proposal of new metadata terms in collaboration with GSC and TDWG.

In October 2025, the task members also had the opportunity to submit an abstract and give an oral presentation at the Living Data 2025 Conference. This effort provided us the opportunity to share with the wider eDNA and biodiversity community the knowledge acquired through the task development. Our presentation focused on the impact of aligning data standards on improving interoperability towards FAIRer eDNA data ecosystems, what alignment models are, key findings and gaps identified, and critical requirements and recommendations for future similar efforts. A detailed breakdown of the main tasks and achievements is provided in Figure 15.

For future alignment efforts in the eDNA domain, and in direct support of the objectives of this report, we recommend prioritising alignment work for the FAIRe-based extensions being proposed to TDWG and GSC. Due to its increasing community adoption and its focus on eDNA data, alignment of FAIRe is considered the highest priority, and initial steps to mobilise this work are currently underway.

As a next step, aligning MixS's environmental extensions with standards in the Earth and Environmental Sciences sphere would be valuable, especially in the context of initiatives aligned under Horizon Europe, such as the Digital Twin of the Ocean mission. To ensure MixS-compliant datasets are readily consumable by large-scale integrative workflows, emphasis should be placed on a core set of spatio-temporal and environmental metadata. These would include precise collection date and time, depth, and geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude), alongside habitat descriptors at both local and broad scales. In addition, linkage to observational data, when available, can significantly enhance the value of MixS records for ecosystem modelling, biodiversity assessments, and cross-domain data integration.

Finally, if this task were to continue, an update to the BCDM-Darwin Core mapping effort in accordance with SSSOM standards would be the most natural progression, building on the work already presented in this report.

Figure 15. Timeline diagram illustrating the principal sub-tasks of Task T3.2 and their respective durations.

5. Recommendations

5.1 General Guidance

eDNA generates highly valuable data. To make project teams' work easier and maximise eDNA's value to the scientific community, the recommendations below should be applied where relevant. Metadata should follow established standards; we recommend the FAIR eDNA (FAIRe) metadata checklist (Takahashi et al., 2025) as a starting point. FAIRe already incorporates terms from the main eDNA standard organisations, especially DwC and MIxS, ensuring interoperability and consistency across datasets.

5.2 Prepare and regularly update a Data Management Plan

As part of the overall programme of work, it is essential to promptly prepare a data management plan (DMP). A DMP provides clarity within the project team about which data needs to be collected, by whom, where and when it should be stored, shared and published. This streamlines data management throughout the project's lifetime, saving time, reducing confusion, and improving the quality and availability of the datasets for the broader community.

A DMP should be considered a living document that is updated throughout the project. Thus, it becomes invaluable project documentation, enabling everyone to trace what data and metadata were collected, how they were processed, and where each dataset was stored and published.

There are numerous general templates and guides available for preparing a DMP, most of which follow similar principles, such as the FAIR principles. For templates and guidance in Europe: see the “researcher guidance for data management” (<https://scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/open-science/research-data-management/>), UK (<https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/learning-hub/research-data-management/plan-to-share/data-management-planning-overview/>) and <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/data-management-plans>), U.S.A. (<https://www.nsf.gov/funding/data-management-plan>). DMP benchmarking can be found in scientific literature, with many focused on biomedical research, but also including broader assessments (Williams et al., 2017).

If a broker is being used, much of the data management may be handled by the service itself. In this case, the project's DMP can be simpler, but users must comply with the broker's standards. Note that attention should be paid to transparency issues from the outset when contracting the service, ensuring that at least the minimum required information about the applied methodology is published to support reproducibility and interoperability of the resulting data. If a broker is not used, we recommend starting with the FAIRe checklist and using the tools it provides to improve the FAIRness of your data.

5.3 Prepare and Submit Raw eDNA Sequences to a Public Repository

We recommend that raw eDNA sequence data, albeit trimmed of technical sequences (i.e., primers and adaptors, when applicable), be submitted to a public sequence archive, ideally to one of the INSDC databases. The submission should include sequencing metadata, such as the sequencing

instrument and whether paired-end or single-end (if relevant), and, ideally, a link to the laboratory protocol.

INSDC suggests that sequences should be uploaded in trimmed form to facilitate mining of raw sequence data. However, we recommend that, whenever possible, primers and adapters also be included in the metadata to support reuse when relevant. Sample metadata, including information on all previous DNA analysis steps, should be submitted via an environmental package or checklist, ideally populated with rich metadata rather than the minimal required fields.

An ideal practice is to begin submitting metadata before sequencing. This practice ensures that details are adequately captured and provides the added advantage of serving as a backstop in the event of unexpected setbacks, such as hard-disk failures or key people leaving. Using your preferred INSDC archive, it is possible to create a BioProject and submit sample metadata, which will provide a BioProject ID and BioSample IDs ready for the submission of sequence metadata. If desired, the release of the BioProject and BioSample metadata can be suspended for up to two years, whilst sequencing, analysis, and manuscript writing are in progress.

5.4 Prepare and Submit Processed eDNA Sequences and Taxonomic Assignments to a Public Repository

Whether using an existing bioinformatics workflow or a custom one, it is good practice to make the workflow publicly accessible on platforms such as protocols.io, WorkFlowHub, GitHub, or Zenodo, and to include its URL when submitting sequences to support reproducibility.

The processed eDNA sequences should be deposited in a public repository and linked to the BioSample ID and the workflow URL, with additional metadata, where possible, to strengthen traceability, including associations with source material and spatiotemporal provenance, in support of Access and Benefit Sharing best practices (building on ongoing efforts such as BiCIKL).

The preferred option for data deposit is an INSDC archive or a biodiversity data aggregator such as OBIS or GBIF, including their respective nodes or brokers. Figure 16 summarises the recommended workflow for sharing and publishing eDNA data. Depositing eDNA data as assigned taxon occurrences in biodiversity platforms like GBIF and OBIS is crucial for maximising the findability and accessibility for users outside the omics expert community, such as biodiversity researchers without molecular expertise and stakeholders in environmental administration or policy. Ensuring broad data availability across all user groups maximises its impact.

Figure 16. Simplified version of the recommended steps to manage and deposit eDNA data.

Note that there is data flow from INSDC (via ENA) to GBIF for environmental sequences and metadata from metagenome datasets, with date and location information recorded. This flow of data

occurs after sequences are processed into occurrences with taxonomy using MGnify and subsequently archived in OBIS (for marine datasets) and GBIF (for all datasets), encompassing approximately 1,000 datasets. MGnify is a free, open-access EMBL-EBI platform that analyses, annotates, and enables exploration and comparison of microbiome and metagenomics datasets using standardised pipelines. When submitting a processed dataset to OBIS and/or GBIF, the link to the raw sequences should be included in the associatedSequences metadata field, thereby preserving the link to the INSDC database.

5.5 Missing Tools

Ideally, there would be a one-stop tool that would automate submission of everything from your institute's local sequence store to submission to the appropriate repositories. This ease is still a pipe dream for much of the community, but there has been remarkable progress.

Some sequencing brokers already offer this, e.g. as presented at the GSC 2025 conference by Philipp Muench (Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research): "*A platform facilitating MixS-compliant metadata collection and data generation for microbial omics projects*".

In the biodiversity world, there is GBIF's Metabarcoding Data Toolkit (MDT) (<https://docs.gbif-test.org/mdt-user-guide/en/>), XLSX templates (<https://github.com/ELIXIR-Belgium/ENA-metadata-templates>), guidelines (<https://fair-edna.github.io/guidelines.html>), and other tools to enable, or at least guide, you through collecting metadata and data, mapping metadata, and generating the appropriate data formats needed to submit data to GBIF and/or OBIS. For metabarcoding data from one of the supported marker regions (e.g., COI, ITS, rbcL), the GBIF MDT Tool also offers the option to apply an integrated taxonomic assignment pipeline based on specific reference sequence libraries (e.g., BOLD, UNITE, Diat.barcode).

GBIF and OBIS are well-positioned to develop additional services for eDNA data submission, storage, and sharing. As established databases with active long-term development communities, the conceptualisation of a 'one-stop shop' for a complete eDNA data workflow is feasible. Indeed, initial discussions on the development of such tools are already underway, and ongoing efforts, such as GBIF's funded work to improve aspects of DNA data storage, including reference library catalogues, demonstrate that this goal is attainable given adequate resources and sustained investment.

At the same time, it is important to distinguish publishing workflows from bioinformatic analysis pipelines. While end-to-end automated pipelines for sequence processing are increasingly feasible, a key challenge remains the widespread reliance on individually customised bioinformatics pipelines, local reference libraries and partly subjective expert decisions across multiple processing steps. As sequencing platforms and analytical methods continue to evolve rapidly, a single, universal pipeline is unlikely to meet the diversity of current and future eDNA use cases. Existing platforms such as MGnify illustrate both the potential and the limitations of centralised analysis services, which are insufficient for many applied eDNA contexts.

We therefore recommend a parallel approach: the continued development of automated pipelines for clearly defined use cases, alongside robust tools, standards and practices that support the submission of well-documented datasets generated through customised processing workflows.

For the future of the eDNA ecosystem, we further recommend that eDNA and biodiversity repositories implement eDNA-specific quality control and validation mechanisms, providing data users with additional, transparent information to better assess the reliability, compatibility, and appropriate reuse of these records. An initial set of recommended criteria could include automated assessments on metadata completeness, for example, by verifying that highly recommended fields are present and consistently populated. In addition, datasets should, where relevant, adhere to recognised standards

across the different steps of the eDNA workflow, including sampling, laboratory procedures, and data analysis. Data providers that consistently and comprehensively report high-quality metadata could benefit from being assigned a validation or reliability score at the dataset or provider level, which would signal the overall trustworthiness of their records. Such a scoring system would not only incentivise best practices in metadata reporting but also provide users with an indicator of data robustness.

For databases aggregating occurrence data, such as GBIF and OBIS, we recommend including taxonomic assignment reliability scores. These could be provided directly by data publishers, together with the methodology used to derive them, as part of the submitted metadata, or alternatively assigned using a repository-intrinsic assessment method. We note that the FAIRe initiative has explored automated assessment of species annotation confidence; however, no consensus has yet been reached on the most appropriate scoring system or indicators to support these values (see https://github.com/FAIR-eDNA/FAIRe_checklist/issues/15). OBIS indicates that this feature is currently in development. Sustained and targeted funding will be essential to support the research, development and community consensus-building required to implement and maintain such frameworks at scale.

In addition, for DNA-derived occurrences, the reliability of the site and sampling time can be evaluated based on the eDNA source (e.g., sediment, water, air, or bulk), as these occurrences may reflect a snapshot of the sampling time rather than a direct observation of the organism. Due to the intrinsic characteristics of eDNA methods, such as transport, persistence, and degradation in different environments, clearly documenting the sampled matrix is essential for correctly interpreting the spatial and temporal relevance of eDNA-based records. Finally, particularly for occurrence databases, such as GBIF and OBIS, the development of community-driven curation mechanisms, such as allowing users to flag potentially suspicious or uncertain records, would add an interactive layer of validation. This approach would be especially valuable for taxa where reference databases are still under active development, and where expert review can improve data quality over time.

5.6 Sustainable Metadata Alignment

To promote interoperability and reduce complexity in metadata reporting, new terms should, whenever possible, be based on existing, established terms rather than creating entirely new fields. Introducing novel terms can fragment the metadata landscape, making integration across datasets and repositories more difficult and increasing the risk of inconsistent usage (Figure 17). While it is normal for the focus of different standards not to fully overlap, such as BCDM focusing on biodiversity and MlxS on sequence data, reusing, modifying or extending existing terms helps maintain alignment across repositories. This approach ensures metadata coherence and supports long-term sustainability, as users and tools can rely on a stable set of terms instead of constantly adapting to repository-specific variations.

When terms are derived from existing standards, they should explicitly indicate the source and version of the originating standard, as well as any transformations applied during integration. Detailed provenance information enables users to trace the origin of each term, understand how it was adapted, and reliably reproduce mappings or analyses. For newly introduced terms, particularly those derived from sources not designated as metadata standards, the rationale for their creation should be documented, including any departures from the source and the reasoning behind them. By combining version tracking, thorough provenance documentation, and careful evaluation of the necessity of new terms, eDNA repositories can support a sustainable metadata ecosystem aligned with community standards.

Figure 17: “Standards”, a comic illustrating the proliferation of standards and the irony of creating a new one to solve the problem of too many existing standards (Munroe, R. (2011)).

Metadata standards and extensions that adopt terms from existing sources should be regularly updated to remain aligned with the latest versions of their source checklists. Memoranda of understanding between key institutions provide a foundation for this coordination; however, if not upheld, their value is compromised. Future MoUs should include clear timelines for updating mappings whenever specifications change, particularly following major releases. Broader community engagement and institutional adoption of mappings can ensure that alignment efforts remain current, open and trusted.

Finally, beyond continuous development and metadata alignment, checklists should also accompany protocol development in the field. As mentioned in section 3.3, FAIRe currently aligns only with metabarcoding and target assays, highlighting the need to expand coverage as protocols evolve.

6. Discussion

This report presents a comprehensive analysis of the current eDNA metadata landscape, focusing on standards within eDNA repositories and combining landscape analysis, stakeholder-driven evaluation of standard usage, and technical alignment work to identify both practical and structural barriers to interoperability. By compiling and comparing the main metadata standards and checklists used for eDNA (meta)data reporting, the work establishes a shared reference point for understanding similarities, gaps and inconsistencies across platforms.

Building on this foundation, stakeholder use-case evaluations assessed the perceived importance and feasibility of metadata requirements for different eDNA data types, providing empirical insights into current submission practices. In parallel, two alignment models were developed as the primary technical outcome of the project. The GBIF/OBIS’s DNA-derived extension, selected as one of the most critical standards for biodiversity data derived from eDNA samples used within GBIF and OBIS infrastructures, was aligned with MIxS Core. In addition, the alignment between the Barcode Core Data Model (BCDM) and MIxS Core was updated in accordance with SSSOM standards in collaboration with the Biodiversity Genomics Europe project, strengthening coordination across initiatives with related objectives and helping avoid duplication of effort.

Close collaboration is also ongoing with the FAIRe initiative to establish mappings between the checklist and the standards from which it was derived. As these mappings will only be formalised following the adoption of the FAIRe-based extension within GSC/TDWG, they fall outside the timeline

of this report. Nevertheless, alignment with existing, widely adopted standards is being actively considered during term revision and proposal, helping enhance interoperability across eDNA metadata standards.

Beyond establishing semantic and syntactic mappings, the alignment models served as diagnostic tools, enabling the systematic identification of structural misalignments, undocumented term provenance, and coordination gaps between standard bodies and biodiversity repositories, all of which pose practical barriers to interoperability. Together with the resulting recommendations for data producers, repositories, and standard communities, this work highlights both immediate opportunities and long-term challenges in advancing a sustainable, interoperable eDNA digital ecosystem.

For larger collections of metadata terms, the team recommends considering automated semantic alignment approaches, such as fuzzy matching. This approach was not adopted in the present work because the number of metadata terms was relatively small and the semantic correspondences were exact matches, making manual mapping faster and more reliable.

The most time-consuming effort was dedicated to the syntactic mappings. Syntactic normalisation is a prerequisite for meaningful interoperability in the eDNA domain, enabling seamless data exchange and reuse across heterogeneous systems. It is also essential for machine-actionable data, supporting more advanced forms of data automation, validation and integration. In an environment where natural language processing is increasingly leveraged, both syntactic and semantic alignment substantially improve the reliability and scalability of automated processing. At present, the team is not aware of any mature, off-the-shelf tools capable of performing domain-specific syntactic alignment without significant development effort, making a largely manual approach unavoidable.

With respect to community involvement and continuity, a key limitation is that the relevant standard bodies (TDWG/GSC) or GBIF have not yet adopted the proposed mappings (i.e., the pull request has not been accepted). As a result, it is currently not possible to track low-confidence mappings through formal issue tracking mechanisms or to discuss them openly with the broader community within those infrastructures. Furthermore, as the eDNAqua-Plan repository will become inactive after the project concludes, these mappings cannot be sustainably discussed or refined there. To address this gap, the effort must either be adopted and maintained by recognised standard bodies or biodiversity infrastructures, or future mapping initiatives will need to fork the repository to sustain community engagement and governance beyond the lifetime of the eDNAqua-Plan project.

Beyond repository governance, long-term interoperability also depends on keeping mappings between key standards, particularly the GSC MixS and DwC core, up to date. Challenges related to MixS-DwC mapping drift are common when independent institutions and initiatives evolve at different paces, especially when comparing core standards with extension checklists. However, given that a memorandum of understanding (MoU) has been established among the involved institutions, such inconsistencies would be expected to occur less frequently and be managed more effectively within the group through coordinated efforts.

At the same time, even when MoU participants align updates internally, institutions and platforms outside this coordination framework may adopt new versions at different times due to limited technical capacity, staffing constraints, or differing priorities. This asynchronous adoption can further exacerbate metadata discrepancies across the broader ecosystem. Additionally, core standards often follow more frequent release cycles, which may outpace extensions' ability to remain fully aligned when their own release schedules are not synchronised, resulting in temporary gaps in compatibility.

The process of proposing and implementing new GSC MixS checklists is also not yet streamlined. This drawback was observed through collaboration with different eDNA-related initiatives, including the FAIRe (<https://fair-edna.github.io>) and the ancient DNA (Minimum Information about any Ancient Sequence, or MINAS) (<https://www.mixs-minas.org/>) projects, and reflects a broader challenge

faced by volunteer-funded standards organisations such as the GSC. Addressing this requires active engagement from requesting communities, with designated contributors working directly with the GSC to help drive checklist development. Significantly, the involvement of new contributors with different perspectives has dramatically improved the quality of existing terminology and enabled the introduction of relevant terms, yielding benefits across multiple communities, for example, by promoting appropriate generalisation and enhancing interoperability.

Similarly, the eDNAqua-Plan project has benefited from a diverse team of contributors and scientific advisors, as well as extensive stakeholder engagement worldwide. This breadth of expertise has been essential in developing recommendations aimed at a more sustainable digital ecosystem, one that reflects the needs of the wider community and the systems that support it. These include data users and researchers, private and governmental institutions, standard organisations, policy makers, data and systems architects, as well as machine-driven workflows and algorithms.

In this report, data users and researchers were engaged through use-case evaluations to assess the required status of metadata terms, providing insight into submission behaviour and community perceptions of mandatory, recommended, and optional metadata. This analysis informs practical guidance on submission practices. It helps identify which metadata terms are more readily accepted for standardisation, as well as where uncertainty or resistance may indicate the need for phased or context-dependent approaches.

For data and system architects, as well as standards organisations, the project delivered two alignment models: the first between the DNA-derived extension and MixS Core, and the second between the Barcode Core Data Model and MixS Core. These models clarify the semantic and syntactic correspondences between standards and lay the foundation for future interoperability efforts. While they enable more precise semantic and syntactic alignment, automated normalisation and conversion tools remain to be developed to support scalable, cross-system data exchange.

By explicitly considering both human and machine consumers of data, the project underscores the importance of inclusive, interoperable, and future-proof design in the development and governance of a sustainable digital ecosystem.

Finally, we acknowledge that addressing the technical interoperability issues examined in this report represents only a first prerequisite towards the large-scale, mainstream application of eDNA data for biodiversity monitoring and the detection of long-term trends and their drivers (Gonzales et al., 2023). An arguably even greater challenge lies in developing robust, reliable practices for integrating datasets generated by highly heterogeneous methods. Even when metadata gaps are fully resolved and data provenance is well understood, fundamental questions remain: how should eDNA-based species records be compared and combined when they are derived from different metabarcoding markers, assigned with varying levels of taxonomic confidence, or originating from samples with differing volumes of filtered water?

While we are optimistic that the continued development of international standards across methodological steps will help reduce methodological diversity over time (e.g. EN 17805:2023; see <https://iestf.global/> for news on aquatic eDNA standard development), addressing these questions will nonetheless require sustained attention and collaboration within the eDNA community in the coming years.

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9. Annexes

Supplementary Figure S1: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the INSDC: GSC MixS miscellaneous natural or artificial environment checklist for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M) and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S2: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the INSDC: GSC MIxS sediment checklist for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M) and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S3: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the INSDC: GSC MIxS water checklist for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M) and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S4: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the INSDC: ENA default sample checklist for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M) and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S5: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the GBIF DwC DNA-derived data extension for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S6: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the GBIF DwC Occurrence core for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S7: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the OBIS DwC Occurrence core for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into recommended. Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S8: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the OBIS DwC Term checklist for OBIS for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Strongly Recommended (SR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S9: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIR Project section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S10: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIR Data Management section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S12: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIR Sample Collection section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S13: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIR Sample Storage section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S14: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIR Sample preparation section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S15: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIR Sample information section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S16: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIR Sample relations section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S17: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIRe Nucleic Acid Extraction section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S18: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIRe Targeted Assay detection section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S19: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIRe PCR section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S20: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIRe Library preparation and sequencing section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S21: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIR Bioinformatics section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

Supplementary Figure S22: Heatmap of responses for metadata field in the FAIR OTU/ASV section for each use case (x-axis). Metadata fields are grouped into Mandatory (M), Highly Recommended (HR), Recommended (R), and Optional (O). Colours correspond to codes defined in Table 2.

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